

D.1.1: Comprehensive Regional Analysis Report

Lead Partner: UNINA

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List of Acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
BioFairNet	Project Acronym: Bioeconomy and Circular Economy Fair Network
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
EU	European Union
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
BIO2REG	Acronym for a related project (Horizon Europe)
EEA	European Environment Agency
PM_{2.5}	Particulate Matter 2.5
JTM	Just Transition Mechanism
S3	Smart Specialisation
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
PDO	Protected Designation of Origin
PM₁₀	Particulate Matter ₁₀
NH₃	Ammonia
CH₄	Methane
N₂O	Nitrous Oxide

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the identification and assessment of three agricultural and mining hotspot regions in the European Union, where environmental pressures, socioeconomic dependencies and transition opportunities converge. The analysis forms a core component of WP1 and provides the knowledge base for the development of transition pathways, the Sustainable Transition Business Model Framework (D1.2), and the digital tools of WP3.

The research identifies also two non-European Union regions very interesting in terms of policy implementation where the models created in relation to the results of the interaction with the EU stakeholders will be validated.

The hotspot identification process is grounded in a systematic review of scientific literature (2015–2025) and an extensive analysis of EU-level grey literature, complemented by environmental data and sectoral statistics. This integrated evidence allowed the mapping of regions where agricultural and mining activities generate significant impacts on greenhouse gas emissions, water and soil resources, air quality, ecosystems and local communities.

The assessment follows a multi-criteria conceptual framework developed within WP1, which combines environmental pressures, sectoral intensity, resource use patterns, socioeconomic vulnerability, and institutional readiness to support bio-circular and regenerative transition models. The selected hotspots exemplify contexts where both environmental degradation and opportunities for systemic innovation are particularly pronounced.

Four priority hotspot regions were identified. In the agricultural sector, Lombardy (Italy) and Andalusia–Almería (Spain) represent high-intensity production systems characterised by strong pressure on air, water and soil resources, concentrated livestock and greenhouse horticulture, and structural exposure to climate change. In the mining sector, the Iberian Pyrite Belt (Spain) and the Rhenish Lignite District (Germany) showcase contrasting challenges linked respectively to legacy contamination, acid mine drainage, and large-scale landscape transformation associated with the lignite phase-out.

The findings of this deliverable support the design of targeted transition actions within BioFairNet, informing the multi-actor engagement strategy, the development of business models and value-chain opportunities, and the formulation of policy insights in subsequent work packages.

In addition to the territorial identification of hotspot regions, Deliverable D1.1 adopts a value chain perspective to analyse how traditional production models and emerging bio-circular value chains interact within the selected hotspots. This approach highlights key transition challenges and opportunities across agricultural, agri-food, biomass-based, and extractive value chains in EU regions. The analysis provides an analytical foundation for subsequent project activities related to business model innovation, co-creation processes, and the development of digital tools under the BioFairNet project. Regions of Canada and Kenya are considered as reference transferability and will be further addressed in subsequent project activities.

The document is structured into several sections, which describe the general structure of the document, the conceptual and methodological framework of the research, and the regional analysis dedicated to the agricultural production and mining sectors, respectively, in the project's hotspot areas.

1. Introduction

The Bioeconomy and Circular Economy Fair Network (BioFairNet) aims to support the transition of greenhouse gas (GHG)-intensive sectors- particularly in mining and agriculture- towards sustainable, inclusive, and circular economic models. By establishing a cooperative digital platform, the project facilitates stakeholder engagement, knowledge sharing, and collaborative action across sectors and regions. BioFairNet seeks to bridge structural gaps between scientific research, public administrations, private actors, and local communities by promoting co-creation processes that combine analysis, knowledge transfer, and collaborative innovation.

The purpose of this report is to deliver a structured and evidence-based assessment of mining and agricultural activities in selected European regions, with the objective of identifying sectoral dynamics, territorial hotspots, and pathways for a transition towards a biocircular economy.

The analysis focuses on two key intervention domains - agricultural production and mineral extraction – whose spatial concentration and intensity of use generate significant socio-economic and environmental pressures.

Building on a systematic review of academic and grey literature, complemented by an examination of relevant EU policy frameworks and regional level data (NUTS-2/NUTS-3), the report evaluates the drivers, impacts, and transformation potentials of these activities. Particular attention is given to areas where patterns of resource exploitation, environmental stress, and socio-economic dependency converge, thus constituting territorial Hotspots within the scope of the BioFairNet project.

Within this framework, the project investigates European regions historically dependent on coal mining and intensive agriculture, with the objective of identifying transformation potentials, sector-specific concepts, and regional pathways for transition. The intention is to provide a solid knowledge base that informs the development of future transition strategies and supports the co-creation of innovative tools for ecological and economic transformation.

This Report establishes the conceptual and territorial foundations for analysing how traditional and bio-circular value chains operate in selected European regions. It aims to advance the understanding of transformation dynamics in GHG-intensive sectors by providing sectoral analyses, identifying key stakeholders, and reviewing both scientific literature and policy-

oriented sources. The findings serve as a reference point for future strategic actions and regional interventions within the scope of the project.

This Deliverable D1.1 is part of Work Package 1 (WP1) – State-of-the-Art Analysis and Assessment Strategy of the BioFairNet project (GA 101181568). WP1 constitutes the theoretical and analytical foundation of the entire project, with the objective of outlining the state of the art of regions with high greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions—particularly in the agricultural and mining sectors—identifying critical points and opportunities for transition, and establishing the methodological basis for the subsequent work packages.

This report is closely connected with several key deliverables of the BioFairNet project, particularly those focused on business models, policy insights, and stakeholder-oriented digital tools. It provides the analytical basis upon which the Sustainable Transition Business Model Framework (D1.2) will be developed, offering essential inputs on sectoral dynamics, regional value chains, and transition potentials in mining regions. The identification of environmental hotspots, stakeholder configurations, and governance patterns presented in this document directly informs the elaboration of transition strategies and business model adaptation in subsequent project activities.

2. Structure of the document

This report is structured to ensure consistency, methodological transparency, and ease of use and consultation for the other project partners and stakeholders involved. For these reasons, it is divided into sections and subsections. The "document structure" section is further enhanced by a graphical representation (diagram), allowing the reader to navigate the document's various sections more intuitively.

The report opens with an Executive Summary, which provides a general explanation of the report's content and purpose in relation to the objectives of Work Package 1 (State of the Art Analysis and Evaluation Strategy), aimed at identifying hotspot regions/territorial areas of the BioFairNet Project.

This is followed by an Introduction that briefly outlines the objectives of the BioFairNet project and Work Package 1, as well as the structure of the research and analysis activities (presented in this report) undertaken to identify the hotspots.

The next section (Paragraph 3) details the research and analysis activities undertaken. It provides a detailed description of the Conceptual Framework, which defines the main factors and criteria needed to identify geographically critical and vulnerable areas, both environmentally and strategically, in order to propose biocircular transition models for the agricultural and mining sectors.

Subsequently, Section 4, "Methodology for Regional Selection," details the methods used to identify hotspot territories across the European Union, both for the agricultural sector (Section 4.1) and the mining sector (4.2). This is done through an in-depth analysis of the most authoritative scientific literature in these sectors and the "grey literature" (Section 4.3), consisting of official EU documents and registers.

Section 5 (Regional analysis and hotspot identification) and its subsections describe the main findings of the analysis of the scientific and "grey" literature, highlighting the main critical issues in the identified hotspot areas (Regions belonging to the European Union), in terms of the intensity of agricultural (section 5.1) and mining (section 5.2) exploitation and the resulting impacts, particularly environmental, of these production activities. The analysis is divided into the two production sectors relevant to the project and each identified hotspot region.

Section 6 (Non-EU Hotspot Regions) is dedicated to the analysis of the non-European Hotspot Region, identified during the design phase as an area for validation and potential replication of the results of the BioFairNet project and the best practices being tested.

Section 7 (Value Chain Perspective across Identified Hotspots) provides a cross-sectional analysis of the main value chains characterizing the identified hotspot regions, with particular attention to the distinction between traditional and emerging biocircular value chains.

The final section consists of Section 8, dedicated to "Connecting this report with other project results," while Section 9 illustrates how the results obtained through this activity relate to other EU-funded projects addressing the same issues as BioFairNet.

The document concludes with an index of references, organized by type of source used in the report. Finally, an additional document containing the "Stakeholder Engagement Plan for the Community Engagement Strategy and Data Collection" is attached.

Document structure diagram

Figure 1 Document Structure Diagram

3. Conceptual Framework

The report conceives regional hotspots as territories where environmental and socio-economic pressures intersect with credible potential for bio-circular and low-carbon transition with specific reference to two productive sectors: agriculture and mining. In BioFairNet, hotspots are not merely areas with critical legacies; they are strategic spaces for transition, where place-based policies, innovation, and stakeholder collaboration can generate outsized benefits in terms of GHG reduction, resource efficiency, and regional resilience.

This perspective aligns with scholarship on sustainability transitions and regional innovation systems, highlighting the role of local institutional capacity, sectoral specialisation, and multi-actor coordination in shaping transition pathways. Bio-circular economy is understood here as an integrated frame that combines biological resource cycles and material circularity, enabling regenerative and inclusive growth patterns. Accordingly, the analysis adopts a three-pillar lens—environmental, economic, and social/institutional—operationalised through indicators and qualitative evidence to identify (i) GHG intensity and environmental externalities; (ii) economic dependence on high-impact sectors; and (iii) adaptive capacity and social sensitivity of communities and institutions. Under this conceptualisation, hotspot identification is both an analytical exercise (mapping pressures, dependencies, and readiness) and a strategic exercise (prioritising regions with high leverage for demonstrators and policy learning). As previously mentioned, the hotspots were identified with specific reference to the agricultural production and mining sectors, and specific criteria were used, which will be explained in detail in the following sections of this deliverable.

3.1 Definition of Regions and Hotspots within the BioFairNet Project

Within the framework of the BioFairNet – Bioeconomy and Circular Economy Fair Network project, the concepts of Regions and Hotspots play a strategic role in structuring and implementing the activities of research, co-creation, and validation. The Regions represent the European pilot territories selected for the experimentation and deployment of the solutions proposed by BioFairNet. These areas serve as territorial contexts where the transition towards bio-circular and low-carbon economic models can be tested through an integrated and

participatory approach. Each Region is characterised by the presence of greenhouse gas-intensive sectors, particularly agriculture and mining/extractive industries, and actively involves local stakeholders — including institutions, enterprises, cooperatives, research entities, and citizens — in co-creation, capacity building, and validation processes. The analyzed Regions therefore act as territorial innovation laboratories, where technological, organisational, and digital solutions for the ecological transition of local value chains are developed and assessed. The results obtained will serve as a foundation for the replication and transferability of the BioFairNet approach to other European and international contexts. The Hotspots are defined as critical areas with high environmental pressure, greenhouse gas intensity, or socio-economic vulnerability, identified as priorities for the implementation and validation of BioFairNet strategies. They include both EU regions and non-EU areas, where the scalability and transferability of developed models are tested. Hotspots therefore act as focal points of intervention and learning, where the BioFairNet digital network concentrates its efforts on data collection, process analysis, and assessment of environmental and socio-economic impacts.

In this sense, the hotspots serve as a dynamic observatory of the challenges and opportunities of the transition towards a fair and circular bioeconomy, contributing to the definition of replicable policy pathways and digital tools at the global level.

4. Methodology for Regional Selection in European Union

The methodology adopted for the selection of the regions was based on the objective of analysing three regions and environmental hotspots within the European Union, with particular attention to the diversity and heterogeneity of the sectors under investigation. The guiding criterion was to identify one region that is strongly representative of environmental degradation for each sector, complemented by a third region in which both sectors are simultaneously present and exhibit critical issues.

The results support the identification of critical environmental hotspots and contribute to the conceptual understanding of how regions with a high intensity of agricultural and mineral

exploitation can transition to circularity and sustainability. These insights, aimed at identifying the territorial Hotspot areas, constitute the necessary prerequisite for the identification and mapping of stakeholders that will be carried out in a subsequent phase of the same Work Package of the BioFairNet Project.

Research approach

Figure 2 Hotspots identification

The relevant contribution of this analysis is the large number of academic literature publications for each sector, integrated by the analysis of the reports and papers published by Economic institutions, Research Centres and European Commission and European Institutions research (defined starting by this point, grey literature).

This methodology of research furnishes a clear and scientific perspective to identification of regions on which the project will be focused.

The Hotspots identified through this assessment, through the considerations and analysis represented in next subparagraph, are:

- for the mining sector: the Andalusia Region (Spain) and the Rhineland (Germany);
- for the agricultural sector: the Lombardy region (Italy), with specific reference to provinces in the Po Valley, and the Andalusian Region (Spain), with specific reference to the province of Almería.

For the mining sector, the Rhineland region in Germany was selected as a representative case of environmentally harmful and unsustainable business models. In the agricultural sector, the Po Valley (Padania) in Northern Italy was chosen due to its significant challenges in terms of biocircularity and environmental performance. The third case study focuses on Southern Spain, a region where both the mining and agricultural sectors are prominent and contribute to complex and interrelated environmental issues, thus providing a fertile ground for comprehensive analysis.

Academic and grey literature have both pointed to Poland as another area of high environmental concern, particularly in relation to mining. Despite the relevance and severity of pollution in that region, the literature also indicates a degree of stakeholder reluctance to engage in biocircularity initiatives. This concern led to the preference for Germany, where similar environmental challenges are present, but where stakeholder engagement is more promising, thereby reducing the risk of limited participation in the development of the proposed model.

With respect to agriculture, the Netherlands was also considered due to its advanced but environmentally intensive agricultural sector. Nonetheless, the Italian case was deemed more suitable, as it more clearly reflects pollution-related issues and suboptimal practices, and thus offers a meaningful opportunity to test the applicability and resilience of biocircularity approaches.

4.1 Agricultural Sector Methodology

Scientific research activities to identify the European Union's environmental hotspots, where agricultural activity has a significant impact, were conducted through the analysis and study of the relevant scientific literature and the so-called "grey" literature, consisting of official documents, reports, and European Union reports on agricultural production activities and environmental sustainability, as well as economic and social sustainability.

First, an initial bibliographic review was conducted of all scientific articles relevant to the topic of agricultural exploitation and its resulting environmental impacts in the various European regions. The search was conducted using the Scopus database, using specific queries and keywords to define the specific scope and time frame from 2015 to 2025.

From this initial selection, a total of 510 articles emerged, of which 62 were found to be closely aligned with the research objectives, 310 were deemed of little use, and 138 were excluded entirely because they addressed topics not relevant to the BioFairNet project.

The selected articles were subsequently analysed and studied in-depth, revealing very interesting evidence that allowed us to identify the main European territorial areas where not only is agricultural exploitation highly prevalent but also has a significant negative environmental impact related to this activity.

Among the most interesting European regions, from this perspective, those highlighted in the scientific literature are Lombardy (Italy) and Andalusia (Spain), which are among the five European regions where the environmental impacts of intensive agricultural activity are most concerning.

For example, data show that Lombardy contributed over 3% of European standard gross agricultural production in 2023, using an agricultural area 22% higher than the EU average (Polis Lombardia, 2024). The environmental impacts generated by this sector are primarily related to: pressure on natural ecosystems and biodiversity (a recent study highlighted that livestock farming in the Po Valley – including Lombardy – contributes significantly to ammonia (NH₃) emissions, which in turn generate fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) harmful to health (CMCC Foundation 2024); overload of benefits and impacts on water and soil; deterioration of air quality (the connection between agriculture, NH₃ emissions, and PM_{2.5} also has repercussions on public health and the environment) (CMCC Foundation 2024).

Andalusia is even considered the top five EU regions in terms of agricultural production, accounting for approximately 3% of Europe's agricultural land and 17% of Spain's total. Therefore, according to industry literature, it represents a key European region, along with the province of Almeria, thanks to the significant investments made since the 1980s to develop innovative greenhouse cultivation techniques. This type of cultivation has generated and continues to generate significant negative environmental impacts. Suffice it to say that today, over 30,000 hectares of greenhouses exist, which, according to industry literature, contribute to significant impacts, such as excessive consumption and exploitation of groundwater, intensive use of technical inputs, massive use of fertilizers and plastics, and pressure on natural ecosystems and biodiversity (Martinez-Blanco, 2019).

These two regions (Andalusia and Lombardy), on the one hand, face significant environmental challenges related to agriculture; on the other, the types of impacts differ significantly, reflecting different local territorial, climatic, and structural conditions.

4.2 Mining Sector Methodology

As a starting point for the development of a monitoring framework, a comprehensive literature review was conducted to identify qualitative factors influencing bio-circular transformations in extractive and mining-related sectors. The analysis focused on mapping the spatial and environmental dimensions of mining activities across the European Union, with attention to regions combining high environmental pressures and potential for sustainable transformation (European Environment Agency [EEA], 2023; European Commission, 2024a).

Given its extensive multidisciplinary coverage in the fields of natural and social sciences, technology, and environmental research, the Scopus database was selected as the primary source. The search combined terms such as *“spatial analysis,” “regional analysis,” “geographical distribution,” “spatial mapping,” “emission mapping”* with *“mining,” “extractive industries,” “waste management,” “mining systems,” “metal extraction,” “mineral extraction,” “refining,” “extraction site,”* and *“mine site.”* To complement this, additional queries included publications containing *“bioeconomy,” “bio-economy,”* or *“biobased economy”* together with *“indicator”* in the title, abstract, or keywords.

The geographical scope was restricted to European Union member states, excluding studies referring to non-European contexts or to permanently abandoned or closed mines, in order to focus on regions where extractive systems remain active or in transition. The review period spanned 2015-2025, corresponding to the timeframe of major EU strategies on industrial decarbonisation, circular economy, and zero pollution (European Commission, 2024b).

The bibliographic search yielded 824 results, of which 130 publications were selected for in-depth analysis based on thematic relevance, methodological quality, and geographic focus. The selected articles were complemented by official and “grey” sources (such as the *Zero Pollution Monitoring and Outlook 2025* (EEA, 2023), the *Raw Materials Scoreboard* (European Commission, 2023), and the *Just Transition Mechanism (JTM) Reports* (European Commission, 2021)), which provide cross-sectoral evidence on mining emissions, soil and water contamination, and regional transition mechanisms. This combined evidence base enabled the identification of territorial clusters where environmental degradation, socio-economic dependence, and transition capacity converge, laying the foundation for hotspot selection.

Comparative evaluation of mining hotspots according to selection criteria (BioFairNet WP1)

Values reflect qualitative assessment from literature and policy analysis.

- Spain strengths: high impact, strong innovation potential, emerging governance.
- Germany strengths: mature governance, strong EU alignment, advanced transition stage.

Figure 3 Comparative evaluation of mining hotspots

The identification of mining hotspots was guided by a multi-criteria assessment framework aligned with the analytical approach adopted for the agricultural sector within WP1. The following ten criteria were used to evaluate the suitability of candidate regions for detailed case study:

1. Environmental impact and pollutant load (e.g., GHG emissions, heavy metals, acid mine drainage);
2. Territorial concentration and continuity (NUTS-2/NUTS-3);
3. Transition status (active, declining, or post-mining phase);
4. EU support mechanisms (e.g., *Just Transition Fund*, *Cohesion Policy*, *Green Deal Industrial Plan*);
5. Administrative and institutional capacity;
6. Political and regulatory alignment with EU transition goals;
7. Social perception and community acceptance of transformation processes;
8. Innovation and circular economy potential;
9. Demonstration value at the European scale;
10. Availability of harmonised datasets and research evidence (Eurostat, 2024).

Based on these criteria, three European mining regions were initially identified: Andalusia (Spain), North Rhine-Westphalia (Germany), and Silesia (Poland). Following qualitative evaluation, Poland was excluded from the shortlist due to weaker administrative capacity, slower transition progress, and limited data availability compared to the other two candidates (Gajdzik et al., 2024; Manowska et al., 2017). Consequently, the Iberian Pyrite Belt (Andalusia) and the Rhenish lignite district (North Rhine-Westphalia) were selected as the final European hotspots for detailed assessment. These two cases embody complementary transition trajectories: the Iberian Pyrite Belt represents a remediation- and innovation-driven pathway centred on circular resource recovery, while the Rhenish lignite district exemplifies a mission-oriented restructuring process grounded in just transition governance. Together, they form the analytical core for assessing extractive-sector transformation within the BioFairNet project.

4.3 The grey literature contribution

In addition to researching scientific literature to identify the European Union's "hotspots" related to the agricultural and mining sectors, we also consulted the grey literature published by the

European Union (particularly reports from European institutions) to identify the regions and territorial areas where agricultural production and mining activities generate particularly significant impacts, not only environmental but also economic and social. Indeed, consulting and analysing this documentation allowed us to better understand the connections between the agricultural and mining sectors and the sustainable bio-circular economy within our research.

In order to review articles which still contain relevant information, only articles published from 2015 to 2025 were included so that we can have information covering a relevant period of time as well as acquiring the most recent results.

Since grey literature is not available through the databases used to search for scientific literature, it was necessary to carry out the search by consulting institutional websites of the European Union. From the consultation of the websites, 324 reports related to agricultural production and 127 on mining were found¹.

A search of websites revealed 324 reports related to agricultural production and 127 to mining. Of these, 37 were considered highly relevant to the project's objectives: agricultural production and 18 to mining.

The identified reports were then analysed and studied in depth to identify potential "hotspot" regions for both the project's sectors (agriculture and mining).

From the initial analyses of grey literature, it emerged that the greatest environmental concerns related to agricultural and mineral production are concentrated primarily in certain regions of Western and Northern Europe and in some areas of Southern Europe (T. Monen et al., 2022).

Specifically, in some Italian and Spanish regions where agricultural and livestock production is highly intensive, as is mining, in the case of Spain and Germany (Buckwell et al., 2014).

The indicators included in the reports are: nitrate concentration in water; ammonia and methane emissions from agriculture; soil nitrogen; fertilizer and pesticide use; high ammonia and nitrate emissions; pollution of groundwater and surface water; soil saturation with nitrates from livestock; loss of river and coastal habitats; and agricultural nitrogen in soil (Soil pollution and ecosystems, 2025).

The indicators related to mining include methane which is a concern for both active and former mines, greenhouse gas emissions (in particular carbon dioxide), nitrogen oxides, sulphur

¹ <https://op.europa.eu/it/web/general-report>.

dioxides, and the pollution of water resources (Enhancing Regional Mining Ecosystems in the European Union: Securing the Green Transition and Supply of Mineral Raw Materials, 2025).

In particular, with regard to the agricultural sector, the reports analysed highlighted that there are intense environmental consequences concerning the Netherlands, where there is an excessive concentration of intensive livestock farming, especially of cattle, pigs, and poultry (Agriculture statistics at regional level - Statistics Explained – Eurostat, 2025).

The reports, including those published by BIO2REG (an EU funded project) also show that Germany produces significant quantities of greenhouse gas (CH₄ and N₂O) emissions (A region heading towards bioeconomy, 2025).

In Spain, especially in Andalusia, a considerable number of pig farms with intensive techniques, especially for export and the excessive presence of greenhouse gases for agricultural production have respectively generated serious pollution of groundwater by nitrates and sewage, a very high-water consumption in semi-arid areas and above all deforestation and the loss of the traditional agricultural landscape. Andalusia is also a leading region in the European Union for the exportation of water intensive crops, despite being one of the driest regions. According to some sources Spain is considered the worst EU country for agricultural nitrate pollution in 2020–2023. (Policies for the Future of Farming and Food in Spain, 2023). The data from Lombardy also appear very interesting where pollution from nitrates and ammonia is evident, especially in the Po (Rapporto Annuale Di Valutazione AI 2022, 2023).

In that area, high emissions of secondary particulate matter (PM₁₀) deriving from agricultural ammonia are recorded, which therefore appears important from a study and research perspective, causing pressure on water bodies and eutrophication problems in the Po Delta and the Adriatic Sea.

The European reports and documents analyzed here highlight that Lombardy represents an area of great interest at the European level due to the impressive intensity of cattle and pig farming, which represents one of the main causes of air and groundwater pollution. (Rapporto Annuale Di Valutazione AI 2022, 2023). Compared to other potential hotspots, the region's geography traps pollutants in place, leading to significant challenges for the Po Valley's air quality. Andalusia on the other hand, has the EU's highest regional agricultural output, primarily based on crops, the equivalent to over 70 percent of its agricultural output value in 2022 (Agriculture statistics at regional level - Statistics Explained – Eurostat, 2025). The European Union views agriculture as a

crucial sector for the economic development of the region of Andalusia but emphasizes the importance of environmental protection (Research for AGRI Committee - Agriculture in Andalusia, 2016). Andalusia is a leading regional exporter for water intensive crops yet is one of the driest regions in the European Union, making it a crucial hot spot to include in the project (Perez, 2025).

Regarding the mining sector, reports clearly show that regional progress is highly dependent on the existence of an intermediate body capable of actively engaging stakeholders. To this end, in the Rhineland region (Germany), an advisory committee composed of twenty members from the region's municipalities has been established to provide additional support to stakeholders and consult directly with these partners (Eutrophication caused by atmospheric nitrogen deposition in Europe, 2024).

It should also be noted that Rhineland's political institutions and industrial networks have developed strategies and systems capable of drastically reducing the use of coal as an energy source, in compliance with the guidelines and timelines set by the European Union. As a result, Rhineland has become the leading mining region in Europe with regard to plans for the complete elimination of coal mining, thanks, as already mentioned, to the particular attention paid to these issues by government institutions and mining industry networks (Regional Development Agency Rhenish Lignite Mining Area - Case study, 2020).

An analysis of European Union reports shows that Poland, like Germany, plays a significant role in the mining sector. However, unlike Germany, Poland has not yet implemented adequate strategies to foster a genuine economic transition in the mining sector. This means that the environmental impacts of mining remain particularly significant, primarily due to the lack of adequate action to reduce coal mining, which remains a major energy source throughout Poland. Unfortunately, Poland is still lagging behind other EU regions in terms of the timelines set by the European Union regarding environmental sustainability. This makes it particularly difficult for the BioFairNet project to engage in timely interaction with various stakeholder groups to effectively implement an environmental transition strategy for the mining sector.

The other region that can be considered a European hotspot for the mining sector is Andalusia (Spain). This region is particularly important not only in the agricultural sector but also in the mineral sector. Mining in this region contributes significantly to eco-sustainability processes in the European Union by providing crucial raw materials, rather than relying on imports of tin,

gold, copper, and lithium from third countries. Similar to agriculture in the region, there are concerns about environmental conservation efforts related to water resources, as the region needs to increase its efforts regarding how the mining sector manages water pollution. The regional government is actively working to address this issue and includes waste remediation efforts in mining contracts (Enhancing regional mining ecosystems in Andalusia, Spain, 2025). In conclusion, it can be stated that the information emerging from the analysis of the grey literature is perfectly consistent with that of the scientific literature regarding the identification of "Hot spot" Regions within the European Union, both for the agricultural and for the mining sectors.

5. EU Hotspot Regions

5.1 Agricultural Sector

Italy - Lombardy (Po Valley quadrilateral: Brescia, Cremona, Lodi, Mantova)

The Po Valley is Italy's largest and most productive agro-industrial corridor, a flat, alluvial basin stretching from the Western Alps to the Adriatic and concentrating more than a third of the national population and roughly a third of national value added (Monteleone & Borzì, 2024; Straffellini & Tarolli, 2023). Within this macro-region, Lombardy's eastern quadrilateral—Brescia, Cremona, Lodi, Mantova—forms the country's densest agro-zootechnical cluster, where high-input arable systems (maize–forage rotations; winter cereals) are tightly coupled with dairy and pig supply chains. The area's infrastructural endowment (irrigation networks, logistics, processing plants) anchors internationally recognized PDO chains (e.g., Grana Padano) and a large upstream–downstream ecosystem (feed, machinery, cold chain, by-product valorisation). Intensive livestock is the keystone: official registries report 470,312 head of cattle in Brescia, 312,730 in Cremona, 116,844 in Lodi, 334,315 in Mantova (end-2021), while the pig herd reaches 1,363,869 in Brescia, 1,102,275 in Mantova, 891,245 in Cremona, 356,031 in Lodi (ERSAF/BDN, 2021).

Figure 4 Livestock and pig populations in the reference provinces. Year 2021

These stocks translate into very high stocking densities at province level (e.g., Cremona 176.6 capi/km²; Lodi 149.2; Mantova 142.8; Brescia 98.3), underscoring the long-recognised “quadrilatero zootecnico.” This structure delivers scale, exports and employment, but also concentrates environmental pressures that define Lombardy as a European-relevant agricultural hotspot.

Figure 5 Densities at province level. Year 2021

On the air-quality axis, the region is emblematic of the Po Valley's nitrate–ammonium chemistry: ammonia (NH_3) from agriculture accounts for ~97% of regional NH_3 ; most originates from livestock (housing/manure), with ~13% attributed to synthetic fertilisers. These emissions drive secondary particulate ($\text{PM}_{2.5}$) formation under stagnant winter conditions (Renna et al., 2024; Colombo et al., 2023). Provincial inventories (INEMAR) reflect the livestock gradient: Brescia ~20–21 kt $\text{NH}_3 \text{ yr}^{-1}$, Cremona 19.4 kt, Mantova ~17–18 kt, Lodi ~9–10 kt (most recent widely comparable release), with agriculture providing >95% of totals in all four provinces. These burdens have documented health externalities across the basin—elevated $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ episodes, excess cardiopulmonary risk, and reduced life expectancy in major urban centres such as Milan (Scotto et al., 2021; Renna et al., 2024; Dang et al., 2024). The regional monitoring network (RRQA) confirms widespread exceedance vs the WHO-2021 guideline; Cremona's annual mean of $25.1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ ranks among the worst in a benchmark of 375 EU cities. Notably, analyses during the 2020 lockdown—with traffic nearly halted—showed limited improvement in air quality, consistent with the stability of agricultural emissions over time.

On the water–soil–climate axis, intensive nitrogen and phosphorus cycling from dairy and pig systems imposes tight constraints on manure management and fertilisation; large portions of lowland UAA lie in NVZs, reflecting chronic eutrophication risks in sensitive waters. Lombardy's agricultural sector also dominates regional non- CO_2 GHG: ~70% of N_2O and ~65% of CH_4 originate from agriculture (2019), concentrated in the eastern plains where intensive livestock prevails. Over 1990–2019, agricultural GHG fell by only ~6% in Lombardy—well below Italy's –17%—signalling slower decarbonisation than national and Po-basin peers. Superimposed on this nutrient-and-emission regime, the 2022 megadrought exposed irrigation fragilities and downstream salinisation risks, underscoring rising aridity and the need to harden water-use efficiency and storage regimes (Montanari et al., 2023; Monteleone & Borzì, 2024). Policy instrumentation is broad but challenged. Three regional pillars structure action: the Nitrates Action Programme (PdA), the Air-Quality Intervention Plan (PRIA), and the Energy, Environment and Climate Programme (PREAC); these dovetail with the CAP/CSR 2023–27. Yet monitoring shows a large residual gap: by 2020, the PRIA had achieved ~922 t NH_3 reduction vs a 2025 target of ~24,605 t, with similarly wide gaps for other pollutants—evidence that incremental deployment has not closed the distance to health-protective concentrations. Recent regional work with ARPA Lombardia/Veneto also indicates that, under WHO-2021 ambitions, continuity

scenarios are unlikely to suffice; modelling suggests that very large herd reductions would be required to meet those thresholds (order-of-magnitude –76% for cattle excluding dairy cows and –68% for pigs), alongside cross-sector cuts—an indication of the stringency implied by health-aligned targets rather than a prescriptive policy stance.

These features jointly justify Lombardy’s selection as a high-leverage “hard-case” hotspot. The region couples very high livestock density (dairy and pig) with policy-relevant externalities and institutional capacity to implement integrated packages. Evidence and practice converge on multi-measure portfolios rather than single “silver bullets”: (i) advanced manure management (rapid removal, covered storages, solid–liquid separation), (ii) anaerobic digestion/biomethane with digestate upgrading and nutrient budgeting, (iii) low-loss application (trailing hose/shoe, injection) and urease inhibitors, (iv) nutrient stewardship & precision agronomy (rate–time–place optimisation), and (v) irrigation modernisation (on-farm efficiency, scheduling, reuse) to reduce CH₄/NH₃/N₂O and water risks—a suite broadly consistent with regional guidance and national “Codice Agricoltura” good practices.

Livestock facilities in Lombardy (Po Valley quadrilateral)

Figure 6 Livestock facilities in Lombardy

Sources: OpenStreetMap contributors (via QuickOSM), administrative boundary (Lombardy)

Complementary circular-economy avenues—co-digesting organic by-products, fertiliser substitution via digestate processing, and reuse of fibre fractions—are already piloted unevenly across the quadrilateral and can be scaled through CAP eco-schemes and regional measures. Finally, while the Po Valley as a whole includes rice districts (e.g., Pavia) and other intensive nodes beyond Lombardy (e.g., Veneto, Emilia), the Brescia–Cremona–Lodi–Mantova block concentrates the dairy–pig nexus most strongly, making it the appropriate NUTS-3 scale at which to plan mitigation–adaptation bundles and to monitor benefits on air quality, nutrient balances, and water productivity (Straffelini & Tarolli, 2023; Arata et al., 2023; Renna et al., 2024; Montanari et al., 2023).

These transition options are supported by a well-established and enabling policy environment. The Po Valley hotspot is included within a consolidated policy framework addressing environmental pressures associated with intensive agricultural and livestock systems. Relevant instruments include the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP 2023–2027), the Nitrates Directive and its regional implementation programmes, as well as regional air quality and nutrient management plans. The area also hosts consolidated good practices related to manure management, anaerobic digestion and biogas production, and the adoption of low-emission agricultural techniques, which provide a robust policy and practice context for the assessment and scaling-up of bio-based and circular transition pathways.

In the Po Valley (Italy), current bioeconomy practices are rooted in an intensive agri-food system where value creation is closely connected to primary production, processing industries, and the management of large volumes of side streams. The Italian strategic framing prioritises integrated value chains and circular solutions that increase the valorisation of residues, by-products and biowaste, while supporting the development of biorefinery pathways that can connect agriculture and processing to higher value bio-based outputs (Fava et al., 2021). The updated Implementation Action Plan reinforces a place-based approach through targeted actions and flagship initiatives, including logistics and pre-treatment capacities for organic streams and measures that strengthen dissemination and monitoring of results and impacts at territorial level (Italian BIT II Implementation Action Plan, 2024). In practice, this configuration points to transition options that depend on coordination along agri-food value chains, mobilisation of side streams at scale, and enabling conditions that make circular deployment operational.

Spain – Andalusia (focus on Almería province)

Regional profile. Andalusia—Spain’s largest region by population and one of its most diverse by geography—extends over ~87,600 km² from Atlantic and Mediterranean coasts to extensive plains and mountain systems, with ~8.4 million inhabitants (Caparrós Martínez et al., 2020). Agriculture and agri-industries are structural to the regional economy (Martinez & Blanco, 2019), yet socio-economic dualisms persist: dynamic coastal/metropolitan belts contrast with inland rural municipalities facing depopulation, unemployment and lower incomes (Caparrós Martínez et al., 2020). Within this mosaic, Almería stands out as a world-class, export-oriented greenhouse horticulture hub embedded in an arid/semi-arid setting—an archetype where productivity, water dependence and material intensity co-locate. The Junta’s official greenhouse cartography (Sentinel-2 based) is the reference used for planning and confirms the extreme concentration of covered agriculture along Campo de Dalías and Níjar–Bajo Andarax, underpinning yearly updates and policy targeting.

Production systems and practices. Region-wide, olive groves dominate land use and value chains (Fernández-Lobato et al., 2024), alongside cereals, fruit-vegetables and industrial crops (cotton) (Soltero et al., 2020). Almonds are expanding with pockets of agro-ecological management, though uptake is uneven given cost and policy constraints (Schoonhoven & Runhaar, 2018). Irrigation is the backbone of competitiveness under a Mediterranean climate with recurrent droughts; it relies on surface withdrawals and groundwater pumping, with rising energy costs and water scarcity risks (Martinez & Blanco, 2019). In Almería, the greenhouse footprint is exceptionally concentrated: the most recent regional inventory reports ~33,400 ha under cover (out of ~40,300 ha in Andalusia), clustered in Campo de Dalías (~22,300 ha) and Campo de Níjar–Bajo Andarax (~9,400 ha). This highly engineered model combines intensive fertigation, climate control and tight logistics to serve EU markets year-round. In parallel, the Cuencas Mediterráneas Andaluzas (CMA) Hydrological Plan 2022–2027 explicitly plans for non-conventional resources—desalination and reclaimed water—in these same sub-systems (Dalías, Níjar, Bajo Andarax), embedding concrete measures in its Programme of Measures.

Greenhouse concentration in Almería (Andalusia, Spain)

Author extraction based on OpenStreetMap (QuickOSM)

Figure 7 Greenhouse concentration

Sources: OpenStreetMap contributors (via QuickOSM), administrative boundary (Andalusia)

Environmental pressures (olive/greenhouse dichotomy). In olive systems, intensification—especially intensive/super-intensive groves with bare-soil management—drives soil erosion, fertility decline and biodiversity loss; restoring ground herb cover improves ecosystem functions and should be mainstreamed (Rey et al., 2019; Fernández-Lobato et al., 2024). In greenhouse districts, the dominant issues are water stress, energy demand and agri-plastic flows: mapping

studies identify southern Spain as a hotspot of agricultural plastic waste, underscoring the need for prevention, collection and recycling infrastructure (Hachem et al., 2024). Water scarcity is the binding constraint across Andalusia: climate change is already reducing rainfall and raising evaporative demand, increasing pressure on aquifers and water quality via return flows with agrochemicals (Martinez & Blanco, 2019). Almería has responded with non-conventional resources: IDAM Campo de Dalías supplies $\sim 30 \text{ hm}^3 \cdot \text{yr}^{-1}$ (the **official upgrade to $40 \text{ hm}^3 \cdot \text{yr}^{-1}$ is approved and included as measure CMA-2003-C in the Plan), and IDAM Carboneras adds $\sim 42 \text{ hm}^3 \cdot \text{yr}^{-1}$. Technical dossiers report specific energy consumption $\sim 4 \text{ kWh} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$ ($\approx 5.17 \text{ kWh} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$ including ancillaries) for Dalías; ACUAMED is also developing on-site PV to target $\sim 35\%$ self-consumption across its desal assets in the area, improving the climate/operating cost profile. In Carboneras, a new dedicated brine outfall has passed environmental screening after the thermal power plant (formerly used for dilution) shut down—routing and conditions now ensure compatibility with protected marine areas (ZEC). Together, these steps alleviate aquifer stress but make efficiency and circularity (on-farm water savings, fertigation recirculation, demand-side management against peak energy tariffs, and brine/return-flow control) central to viable pathways.

Beyond water, agri-plastics are a signature material footprint of Almería’s model. The PIRec-2030 (Andalusia’s Integrated Waste Plan) treats agricultural plastics as a priority stream, defining targets and instruments for prevention, collection and recycling; the regional “Líneas de actuación” for horticulture operationalise actions with producers and waste managers (e.g., organised collection, treatment routes, and eco-design guidance). The greenhouse cartography is used to quantify covered area (and thus expected plastic flows) and to guide oversight at municipal and provincial levels. These instruments give the policy hooks needed to scale circular pilots beyond voluntary schemes.

Hotspot rationale (environment–economy–society).

Environmental. Andalusia integrates two high-pressure archetypes: (i) olive-dominated landscapes with erosion/biodiversity trade-offs, and (ii) greenhouse clusters with acute water–energy–materials intensity. In Almería, the desalination pivot reduces groundwater stress yet shifts the challenge to energy costs, emissions and brine management, now addressed through CMA measures, BOE-recorded environmental resolutions (Dalías capacity increase; Carboneras outfall), and PV self-supply projects.

Economic. Margin compression from irrigation and electricity costs constrains the adoption of improved practices, especially under drought triggers when dependence on non-conventional resources rises—precisely the situation anticipated in the CMA Drought Plan and Cost-Recovery Annex (Anejo IX) that frame tariffs and environmental/resource costs.

Social. A persistent rural–urban divide leaves inland communities with fewer opportunities and greater exposure to environmental costs (Caparrós Martínez et al., 2020). Transition strategies must therefore pair environmental measures with local employment, skills and service provision to avoid further rural decline, and make cost-recovery signals (who pays what) explicit to sustain social acceptance.

Transition levers (place-based, sector-specific). In olive systems: (1) ground cover management and contour farming to curb erosion; (2) precision fertilisation and organic amendments to rebuild soils; (3) olive by-product valorisation (pruning residues, pomace) for bioenergy/biomaterials (Soltero et al., 2020); (4) integrated pest management and varietal/landscape diversification to reduce climate-amplified risks (Ponti et al., 2024). In greenhouse systems (Almería): (1) irrigation efficiency & recirculation, with monitoring at plot level; (2) energy efficiency and on-site PV and demand-response to smooth desalination/irrigation peaks (anchored in ACUAMED PV initiatives and CMA measures); (3) circular plastics via PIRec-2030 instruments (eco-design, closed-loop collection and recycling) and municipal enforcement; (4) nutrient stewardship in fertigated systems to minimise off-site loads. Given Andalusia’s intra-regional heterogeneity, NUTS-3 targeting (e.g., Province of Almería) is essential for measurable outcomes, while NUTS-2 (Andalusia) remains the right scale for programme alignment and financing.

Why Andalusia (and Almería) qualify as agricultural hotspots. The region concentrates multiple, interacting constraints—water scarcity, energy-linked costs/emissions, soil/biodiversity trade-offs, and material footprints—within globally relevant value chains (olive oil; winter horticulture). Almería epitomises a “testbed” hotspot for water–energy–materials circularity under climate stress, with hydrological planning + BOE-level environmental decisions giving auditable milestones ($\text{hm}^3 \cdot \text{yr}^{-1}$ produced/allocated, $\text{kWh} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$, % PV self-supply, outfall compliance). Olive-dominated interiors represent “harder” landscape-level transitions focused on soils and biodiversity. No single measure can deliver the shift: bundled interventions—linking resource efficiency, circularity, risk management and social safeguards—are necessary to maintain

competitiveness while reducing externalities (Martinez & Blanco, 2019; Fernández-Lobato et al., 2024; Caparrós Martínez et al., 2020).

Key figures (most recent available): greenhouses (Almería) ~33.4k ha (of ~40.3k ha Andalusia); sub-areas Campo de Dalías ~22.3k ha; Campo de Níjar–Bajo Andarax ~9.4k ha. Desalination: Campo de Dalías ~30→~40 hm³·yr⁻¹ (design energy ~4–5.17 kWh·m⁻³; PV self-supply target ~35%); Carboneras ~42 hm³·yr⁻¹, with new brine outfall approved.

These structural pressures and quantified targets are embedded within a robust and multi-level policy framework. The Andalusia–Almería hotspot operates under EU and national strategies on water management, circular economy and climate adaptation, including River Basin Management Plans under the Water Framework Directive, regional hydrological planning instruments, and environmental authorisations published at BOE level. This policy context supports the deployment of good practices already present in the region, such as advanced irrigation and fertigation systems, desalination coupled with renewable energy integration, plastic waste collection and recycling schemes from greenhouse agriculture, and initiatives for soil protection and biodiversity conservation in olive-dominated landscapes. Together, these policies and practices provide a clear and auditable governance framework for assessing, scaling and monitoring bio-based and circular transition pathways under conditions of acute resource scarcity.

5.2 Mining Sector

Spain, Andalusia (Iberian Pyrite Belt)

Andalusia, Spain's southernmost autonomous community, integrates a complex mosaic of environmental, industrial, and socio-economic systems that make it one of Europe's most emblematic regions for studying the interface between extraction, energy transition, and circular economy. Within this macro-region, the Iberian Pyrite Belt (IPB) forms a vast metallogenic corridor across the provinces of Huelva and Seville, historically recognised as one of the world's richest sulphide provinces. Copper, zinc, and lead extraction have driven local industrialisation and international trade since the nineteenth century, leaving behind one of the continent's most extensive and persistent mining legacies. Centuries of extraction and smelting have generated open pits, tailings, and oxidation ponds that continue to discharge acid effluents loaded with

metals into the Tinto and Odiel river basins (Ruiz Cánovas et al., 2020; Luís et al., 2024). The distinctive red hues of the Río Tinto, caused by ferric iron precipitation, are a visual testament to this deep alteration of geochemical and hydrological systems.

The IPB lies within an Andalusian context characterised by strong contrasts between coastal industrialisation and inland rural fragility. Although the region is now a key player in Spain's renewable energy expansion, with solar and wind sectors rapidly growing, its economy remains tied to high material and energy intensity. Greenhouse gas emissions in Andalusia are driven predominantly by transport and energy generation, but industrial processes and residual mining activities still contribute to regional totals (Caparrós Martínez et al., 2020). The mining corridor of Huelva, in particular, remains one of the areas where extractive residues and industrial emissions coexist, aggravating local air-quality deterioration and health vulnerabilities. Chronic exposure to fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) and trace metals has been linked to elevated respiratory and cardiovascular risks, especially near legacy mining towns and smelting areas (Sánchez de la Campa et al., 2020; Blondet et al., 2019).

These environmental and health pressures are mirrored by socio-economic asymmetries. The IPB includes small municipalities heavily dependent on declining mining employment and isolated from the diversified economies of the Andalusian coast. Such structural conditions have constrained both investment and policy continuity, leading to fragmented remediation efforts. While several projects, ranging from soil stabilisation to constructed wetlands and pilot biomining, have achieved localised improvements, they remain disconnected from basin-scale planning and from broader frameworks such as the *Estrategia Española de Economía Circular* and the *Estrategia de Transición Justa* (Aguilar-Garrido et al., 2023; Cozma et al., 2024; Perni & Martínez Paz, 2023).

Active mining sites in Andalusia (Spain)

Figure 8 Active mining sites in Andalusia

Sources: OpenStreetMap contributors (via QuickOSM), administrative boundary (Andalusia)

At the governance level, overlapping competences among basin authorities, the regional administration, and local municipalities hinder an integrated response. As Luís et al. (2024) highlight, the absence of a unified hydrological remediation plan allows diffuse contamination to persist across interconnected catchments. Although Andalusia’s environmental policy formally aligns with the Water Framework Directive and the Zero Pollution Action Plan, implementation is still largely project-based and short-term. The result is a patchwork of initiatives that focus on compliance rather than on systemic transformation, leaving structural pollution sources active and unmonitored in the long run.

Despite these limitations, the IPB holds exceptional potential as a testbed for circular and bio-based approaches. Its combination of extensive contamination, strong research infrastructure, and policy experimentation offers a unique laboratory for piloting low-impact remediation and metal recovery. The University of Huelva, together with regional research centres, is developing biomining, phytoremediation, and metal biorecovery processes that could convert waste streams into resources (Delplace et al., 2020; Cozma et al., 2024). At the same time, heritage

valorisation projects such as the restoration of historical railways and industrial sites show that mining identity can be repositioned within cultural and eco-tourism frameworks (Romero Macías & Terrones Saeta, 2024).

Ultimately, the IBP qualifies as an environmental hotspot not only for its ecological degradation but also for the governance and innovation challenges it encapsulates. It condenses within a single territorial corridor the structural contradictions of Europe's industrial peripheries: high environmental liabilities coexisting with technological and institutional potential.

The Iberian Pyrite Belt is framed by European and national policies addressing soil and water protection, pollution prevention and environmental remediation, including the Water Framework Directive and the EU Zero Pollution Action Plan. In this context, the area has become a testing ground for good practices related to bioremediation, phytoremediation and the recovery of valuable materials from mining residues. These initiatives provide a relevant policy and operational background for exploring bio-based remediation and circular approaches in post-mining environments.

Within the BioFairNet framework, the IPB exemplifies the type of high-risk, high-potential region where circular transition could yield systemic benefits if governance, research, and investment align. Realising this potential will require a shift from fragmented projects to long-term basin governance, cross-sectoral financing, and stakeholder co-creation mechanisms. By embedding bio-circular innovation within remediation and regional development strategies, Andalusia's mining corridor could move from being a symbol of extractive decline to a model of ecological and social regeneration consistent with the European Green Deal and cohesion policy objectives. In Andalusia (Spain), current bio-circular practices are visible along two complementary transition arenas located in different parts of the region. One arena is the agri-food hotspot centred on the Province of Almería, where intensive horticultural production and associated processing activities generate large biomass flows and side streams. Sayadi Gmada et al. (2025) describe how regional circular bioeconomy governance aims to mainstream circular practices in such agri-food systems by promoting valorisation of agri-industrial side streams and by strengthening enabling conditions for higher value applications, including logistics and industrial integration (Sayadi Gmada et al., 2025). This regional picture is consistent with economy-wide evidence showing that agriculture and food processing remain the structural backbone of Spain's bioeconomy, implying that new bio-based activities tend to develop in close connection with

incumbent agri-food value chains (Ferreira et al., 2023). A second arena is the mining hotspot associated with the Iberian Pyrite Belt, where circular configurations are linked to the management of acid mine drainage and related environmental risks. Aguilar-Garrido et al. (2023) discuss remediation approaches that mobilise locally available waste streams, including mining, urban and agro-industrial residues, within solutions such as technosols and permeable reactive barriers. This illustrates how circular practices in Andalusia can also emerge through cross-sector resource use that supports environmental risk management in mining affected landscapes (Aguilar-Garrido et al., 2023).

Germany, North Rhine-Westphalia (Rhenish Lignite District)

North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW) has long represented the industrial engine of Germany and a cornerstone of European energy production. Within this Land, the Rhenish lignite district extends across the administrative areas of Rhein-Erft-Kreis, Düren, and Rhein-Kreis Neuss, forming the largest open-cast mining system in Europe. For decades, lignite extraction and combustion have been the pillars of regional growth, providing energy security and industrial employment while profoundly reshaping the physical and socio-economic landscape. Massive excavation voids, settlement relocations, and land subsidence testify to a century of extractive intensity that has left an enduring environmental imprint (Gerwin et al., 2023). The region's identity remains deeply tied to its energy heritage: lignite shaped not only the economy but also labour culture, settlement morphology, and political alliances, creating a dense territorial path dependence that continues to influence the present.

The environmental legacy of the Rhenish district is characterised by extensive soil degradation, hydrological disruption, and atmospheric emissions. Open-pit operations have required continuous dewatering, lowering the groundwater table and altering regional hydrology (Küster et al., 2023). The resulting residual lakes, although planned as components of post-mining rehabilitation, raise new geotechnical and ecological challenges, from slope instability to water quality maintenance (Dahmen, 2025). Biodiversity loss and the transformation of agricultural land into degraded zones have been compounded by the atmospheric impacts of power generation, historically contributing to Germany's carbon footprint (Brodny & Tutak, 2020). In recent years, however, active mining areas have entered a progressive closure phase, and environmental restoration has become a structural policy objective rather than a technical afterthought. As Leuchner et al. (2024) observe, the adoption of ecosystem services frameworks

has helped align ecological remediation with social and economic value creation, embedding nature-based regeneration within planning processes.

These processes occur under a robust institutional and legislative umbrella. The German *Coal Phase-Out Act* and the *Structural Strengthening of Mining Regions Act* (both 2020) have institutionalised a mission-oriented approach that explicitly links climate neutrality with regional regeneration. The Rhenish lignite basin thus stands as one of the few European regions where a national decarbonisation mandate is directly coupled with place-based implementation. Coordination is channelled through the *Zukunftsagentur Rheinisches Revier*, a dedicated regional agency that orchestrates funding, project development, and stakeholder participation across multiple governance levels (Becker et al., 2022; Greiving et al., 2022). This model exemplifies how national missions can be spatially translated through multi-level governance, an achievement made possible by Germany's long tradition of federal cooperation and regional planning capacity. Yet even with this strong governance framework, the spatial dynamics of transition remain uneven. Not all municipalities benefit equally from the transformation: some have attracted investment in renewable energy, research infrastructure, and green industry clusters, while others still face uncertainty over employment, land use, and identity. The socio-economic structure of the district (shaped by decades of dependency on lignite) continues to constrain diversification. Community perceptions of the phase-out often oscillate between optimism for new opportunities and apprehension about social displacement (Radtke & David, 2024). These tensions illustrate that the just transition is not only an economic process but also a profound cultural negotiation over territory and future.

Active mining sites in North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW)

Author extraction based on OpenStreetMap (QuickOSM)

Figure 9 Active mining sites in North Rhine – Westphalia

Sources: OpenStreetMap contributors (via QuickOSM), administrative boundary (North-Rhine Westphalia)

***Notes for North-Rhine Westphalia and Andalusia maps:** “Active” = features not tagged as disused/abandoned in OSM at time of extraction.

Environmental rehabilitation itself unfolds along long-time horizons. Recontouring of the pits, reforestation, and rewetting operations proceed gradually, constrained by technical complexity and funding continuity. Hydrological restoration is emerging as a major challenge for post-mining management, given the interplay between climate change, water demand, and the stability of residual lakes. Comparative studies with the Lusatian lignite basin highlight that, while NRW benefits from higher innovation capacity and institutional stability, the environmental magnitude of restoration remains comparable, reminding policymakers that the transition from extractive to regenerative landscapes requires not only investment but adaptive governance and long-term monitoring (Gerwin et al., 2023; Dahmen, 2025).

The Rhenish lignite district thus qualifies as both an environmental hotspot and a policy innovation zone. Its transition exemplifies how large-scale industrial restructuring can be steered through mission-oriented policies that integrate decarbonisation with social and ecological renewal. The redefinition of land uses, toward renewable energy production, reforestation, and

multifunctional spaces, illustrates a shift from extraction to regeneration, from mono-industrial dependency to diversified circular economies. Nevertheless, maintaining momentum will require stable political consensus, the coordination of federal and regional resources, and the inclusion of civil society in the governance of transformation.

In particular, the Rhenish Lignite District represents a hotspot strongly shaped by policy-driven transition processes, notably under the EU Just Transition Mechanism and the German coal phase-out framework. Regional and national programmes support economic diversification, environmental restoration and the reuse of former mining areas. Established good practices include large-scale land rehabilitation, ecosystem restoration and the integration of renewable energy solutions, positioning the region as a key reference for policy-led and socially inclusive transition pathways.

From the perspective of *BioFairNet*, the Rhenish lignite basin represents a mature case of mission-driven regional transformation that offers transferable lessons for other European extractive regions. It demonstrates that successful transition depends not only on funding but on the interplay between institutional coherence, stakeholder collaboration, and knowledge-based innovation. The region's capacity to embed circular models, ranging from the reuse of mining residues to the integration of renewable energy and landscape restoration, positions it as a European laboratory of post-extractive resilience. At the same time, its experience underscores that the spatial dynamics of transition remain uneven and contingent on local agency. For Europe's broader agenda of industrial decarbonisation and territorial cohesion, the Rhenish district provides both a benchmark and a cautionary tale: structural change can succeed when it is mission-led and regionally owned, but its social and ecological balance must be continuously recalibrated through inclusive governance and long-term adaptive planning.

In North Rhine Westphalia (Germany), current practices are strongly shaped by cluster and infrastructure models that connect research, piloting, and industrial collaboration. Schurr and Slusarczyk (2022) describe how the Bioeconomy Science Center provides shared pilot and analytical infrastructures and supports science to business pathways, influencing the emergence and maturation of regional bio-based activities. In the Rheinisches Revier, Hilgert et al. (2025) document an early transition phase where the bioeconomy is discussed as part of the wider structural change associated with lignite phase-out. Practices and expectations emphasise resource efficiency, circular use of side streams, and key enabling technologies including

digitalisation and biotechnology, while recognising that many initiatives remain in a take-off stage rather than mature deployment (Hilgert et al., 2025). This hotspot combines an innovation and piloting ecosystem with the additional complexity of a structural transition context, where credibility depends on implementation capacity, social legitimacy, and the ability to translate projects into territorially anchored economic activity.

Indicator	Spain – Iberian Pyrite Belt (Andalusia, ES61)	Germany – Rhenish Lignite District (NRW, DEA2)
<i>NUTS Region</i>	NUTS2: Andalusia; NUTS3: Huelva, Seville	NUTS2: Köln; NUTS3: Rhein-Erft-Kreis, Düren, Rhein-Kreis Neuss
<i>Extraction type</i>	Polymetallic sulphides (Cu, Zn, Pb)	Lignite (open-cast coal)
<i>Legacy issues</i>	Acid mine drainage (AMD), metal contamination	Land subsidence, hydrological disruption
<i>Main environmental pressures</i>	Water and soil pollution, PM emissions	Landscape loss, GHG emissions
<i>Transition stage</i>	Active remediation and pilot biomining projects	Coal phase-out, mission-oriented restructuring
<i>Government framework</i>	Regional management, fragmented basin authorities	Multi-level governance via Zukunftsagentur Rheinisches Revier
<i>EU Policy alignment</i>	Cohesion Policy, Green Deal, Zero Pollution	Just Transition Fund, Industrial Strategy
<i>Circular potential</i>	Metal recovery, bio-remediation, heritage tourism	Renewable energy integration, reuse of mining residues

Table 1 Comparative regional profile table

5.3 Sustainability bottlenecks emerging from the evidence

Despite contextual differences, the evidence converges on recurring sustainability bottlenecks that shape transition feasibility across hotspots. Cluster-based research shows that circular bioeconomy practices are more advanced upstream and midstream than in downstream phases such as product design, use-phase strategies, and end-of-life arrangements. Stegmann et al. (2020) emphasise that this imbalance is reinforced by traceability challenges for bio-based flows and by limited integration of circular requirements beyond production-side changes (Stegmann et al., 2020). In Italy, this bottleneck appears in the emphasis on enabling conditions for residue

and biowaste valorisation, including evidence needed for end-of-waste approaches and practical traceability mechanisms that can support reliable circular deployment (Fava et al., 2021; Italian BIT II Implementation Action Plan, 2024). In the Rheinisches Revier, Hilgert et al. (2025) similarly report that regulatory arrangements and market uncertainties can hinder the use of side streams and slow circular implementation (Hilgert et al., 2025).

A second bottleneck concerns the transition from pilots to scalable business activity. The European strategic framing recognises persistent barriers related to scale-up, investment risk and market uptake, which are echoed in the Italian and Andalusian contexts through the need for enabling infrastructures, clearer market pull conditions, and financing instruments that are compatible with innovation-oriented pathways (European Commission, 2025; Fava et al., 2021; Sayadi Gmada et al., 2025). In North Rhine Westphalia, the strong role of pilot infrastructures and science to business pathways implies that transition speed depends on access to demonstration capacity, collaboration mechanisms, and the ability to build investable pipelines from research to deployment (Schurr and Slusarczyk, 2022).

A third bottleneck relates to systemic sustainability constraints and the management of trade-offs. Liobikienė and Miceikienė (2023) stress that biomass is finite and climate vulnerable, and that sustainability claims can be undermined by land use change dynamics, carbon sink accounting challenges, biodiversity pressures and food security concerns (Liobikienė and Miceikienė, 2023). D'Adamo et al. (2022) highlight complementary issues in the context of energy-related bioeconomy pathways, where social acceptance and distributional concerns can influence local viability (D'Adamo et al., 2022). In mining affected contexts, Aguilar-Garrido et al. (2023) illustrate that remediation-oriented circular solutions must also manage environmental risks linked to contaminants and long-term effectiveness, which can create additional constraints for business model viability (Aguilar-Garrido et al., 2023).

Finally, governance and legitimacy emerge as cross-cutting constraints. Lühmann and Vogelpohl (2023) argue that German bioeconomy implementation has often struggled to translate strategy into broader socio-ecological transformation due to fragmentation, limited mainstreaming into adjacent policy fields, and weak societal embedding (Lühmann and Vogelpohl, 2023). In Andalusia, Sayadi Gmada et al. (2025) similarly emphasise awareness, coordination and knowledge to business linkages as conditions for sustained uptake (Sayadi Gmada et al., 2025). The JRC state of play shows that awareness raising and coherence building are among the most

frequently cited actions across national strategies, signalling that legitimacy and coordination challenges remain widely recognised across countries (European Commission Joint Research Centre, 2025).

6. Non-EU Hotspot Regions

In accordance with the objectives of Task 1.1, this section extends the comprehensive research and hotspot identification beyond the European Union by including two non-EU regions characterized by high greenhouse gas (GHG) intensity and significant socio-economic dependence on primary production activities.

The inclusion of non-EU regions supports the comparative and transferability objectives of the BioFairNet project, enabling the analysis of transition dynamics under different institutional, economic, and governance conditions, while maintaining coherence with the overall assessment framework applied to EU regions.

The identification of non-EU hotspots was based on desk-based research, including scientific literature, international institutional reports, and publicly available datasets. Selection criteria focused on environmental pressure, relevance of traditional value chains, exposure to transition challenges, and emerging potential for bio-circular and low-carbon solutions.

6.1 Canada – Greater Montréal Agri-Food System

Canada was identified as the non-EU hotspot region under Task 1.1 with a specific focus on agricultural and agri-food value chains characterised by high levels of production intensity, resource use, and growing relevance for bioeconomy-oriented transition pathways, such as the federal plan “A Healthy Environment and a Healthy Economy” which aims to achieve a structural reduction in greenhouse gas emissions in order to reach climate neutrality by 2050, strengthening the climate resilience of communities, production systems and territories by reducing exposure to the physical risks of climate change, and integrating natural and biological resources into sustainable development pathways, in line with the principles of the circular economy and the bioeconomy. As a result, the value of agriculture in Canada has reached approximately \$70.10 billion in recent years (source: Our World in Data).

Within this context, the Greater Montréal area represents a particularly relevant case due to the concentration of agricultural production, food processing activities, and innovation ecosystems embedded in a metropolitan and peri-urban setting.

The agricultural and agri-food system surrounding Montréal plays a central role in regional and national food supply chains, while facing increasing environmental pressures related to land use, nutrient management, greenhouse gas emissions, and food loss and waste generation. These pressures are compounded by climate variability and by the need to ensure food security within densely populated areas.

At the same time, the Greater Montréal region has been actively engaged in the development of circular bioeconomy solutions. The local agri-food innovation ecosystem includes research institutions, technology providers, and public initiatives focusing on precision agriculture, agtech development, organic waste valorization, and the transformation of agricultural by-products into bio-based outputs. Scientific research highlights the role of advanced agricultural technologies and biological processes in reducing the environmental footprint of food systems and improving resource efficiency across the value chain (Montréal International, 2023; Université de Montréal, 2023).

From a socio-economic perspective, the agri-food sector represents a significant source of employment and economic value, while also being exposed to structural challenges related to market concentration, the inclusion of small and medium-sized producers, and the transition towards more sustainable production models. These dynamics closely mirror those observed in several European agricultural hotspot regions analyzed under Task 1.1, supporting the comparative dimension of the BioFairNet project.

6.2 Kenya

Kenya's involvement in the project stems from its importance in the resource-intensive agricultural economy, as a primary and central sector in the country's economy in terms of employment, security and development. Agriculture is one of the main contributors to Kenya's national GDP (currently KES 392,593 million) and is central to the country's political agenda. According to the Kenya Climate Smart Agriculture Strategy 2017-2026, the main objectives in recent years have focused on increasing the sustainability of agricultural productivity, strengthening adaptive capacity and reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Statistical data from

Our World in Data provides clear evidence of the promises made in this plan: the gross value of agricultural production, measured in current US dollars for Kenya, has increased in recent years to £22 billion, also increasing the agricultural value added per worker to £2,299.64. However, it should be acknowledged that high exposure to physical risks from climate change, inefficient management of agricultural residues and limited access to circular economy models and technologies are challenges that must be considered. All these factors make Kenya a relevant hotspot for analyzing bio-circularity pathways oriented towards social justice, closely linked to value creation and the enhancement of rural communities. The analysis conducted in WP1 also tests the BioFairNet model in emerging contexts, characterized by significant technological and institutional asymmetries compared to the EU, providing important validation for the model itself.

7. Value Chain Perspective across Identified Hotspots

In line with the objectives of Task 1.1, Table 2 offers a structured overview of the hotspot regions identified within the BioFairNet project, covering EU regions and two non-EU regions selected for comparative and transferability purposes.

Sector	Region	Country	EU / Non-EU	Main Environmental Pressures	Socio-economic Relevance	Transition Potential
Agriculture	Lombardy (Po Valley)	Italy	EU	Air pollution, water and soil stress, GHG emissions	High employment, integrated agri-food value chains	High
Agriculture	Andalusia–Almería	Spain	EU	Water scarcity, soil degradation, plastic waste	Export-oriented intensive farming systems	High
Mining	Iberian Pyrite Belt	Spain	EU	Legacy contamination, acid mine drainage	Mining-dependent territories	Medium–High
Mining	Rhenish Lignite District	Germany	EU	Landscape transformation, GHG emissions	Regions under Just Transition frameworks	High
Agriculture	Greater Montréal Area	Canada	Non-EU	Land use, nutrient management, food waste, GHG emissions	Major agri-food hub and innovation ecosystem	Medium–High
Agriculture	Rift Valley & Central Highlands	Kenya	Non-EU	Water stress, soil degradation, climate vulnerability, inefficient residue management	High employment, dominance of smallholders, export-oriented value chains	High

Table 2 Identified Hotspot Regions under Task 1.1

In line with the objectives of Task 1.1, this section provides a cross-cutting analysis of the main value chains characterising the identified hotspot regions, with a specific focus on the distinction between traditional and emerging bio-circular value chains. This perspective complements the territorial analysis by highlighting how production, processing, and resource use are organised along the value chain and where transition opportunities may emerge.

7.1 Traditional Value Chains

Across the analysed hotspot regions, traditional value chains are predominantly characterised by linear production models, high resource and energy intensity, and strong dependence on external inputs. In agricultural hotspots, such value chains are typically structured around intensive primary production, centralised processing, and long supply chains, resulting in significant pressures on land, water, and ecosystems. In mining regions, traditional value chains are dominated by extractive activities with limited integration of downstream value creation and long-term environmental liabilities.

These traditional configurations are often reinforced by existing infrastructures, market structures, and policy frameworks, creating structural lock-ins that hinder rapid transformation.

7.2 Emerging Bio-Circular Value Chains

In parallel, several hotspot regions show the emergence of bio-circular value chains aimed at improving resource efficiency and reducing environmental impacts. These include the valorisation of agricultural residues and organic waste, nutrient recovery processes, bio-based product development, and forms of industrial symbiosis linking primary production with secondary processing and waste management activities.

Such bio-circular value chains are typically more place-based, rely on local biomass availability, and involve a wider range of actors, including small and medium-sized enterprises, research institutions, and local authorities. Their development is often supported by targeted policy instruments and innovation programmes, although their scale remains limited compared to traditional value chains.

7.3 Value Chain Transformation Potential

The analysis of value chains across hotspot regions highlights significant variation in transition potential. Regions with diversified economic structures and strong innovation ecosystems show greater capacity to integrate bio-circular solutions along the value chain, while regions characterised by high sectoral dependency and limited institutional capacity face more pronounced barriers.

Overall, the transformation of value chains emerges as a gradual and context-specific process, requiring coordinated interventions across production, processing, governance, and market dimensions. The insights generated under Task 1.1 provide a foundation for subsequent BioFairNet activities focused on business model innovation, co-creation processes, and the development of digital tools supporting sustainable value chain transitions

8. Connection to other deliverables

Deliverable D1.1 contributes specifically to the implementation of Task 1.1 – Comprehensive Research and Hotspot Identification, which involves collecting and analysing data from three European regions and two non-EU regions to identify hotspots within traditional and bio-circular value chains. This analysis plays a central role in defining transition pathways and understanding the territorial, economic, and social characteristics of the areas involved.

Furthermore, the work presented in this document provides the knowledge base necessary for the following tasks within WP1, including:

- Task 1.2 – Business Model Analysis, aimed at analysing existing business models and defining criteria for their transformation towards sustainability.
- Task 1.3 – Identification of Existing Toolkits, dedicated to mapping and assessing methodological tools already available to support the bio-circular transition.
- Task 1.4 – Workshop with Stakeholders, which involves engaging local actors from the target regions to collect needs, perceptions, and contributions for the design of the transition pathway.
- Task 1.5 – Construction of the Co-Creation Model, focused on developing a co-creation model based on the evidence gathered in the previous activities and validating it with experts and stakeholders.

The integration of these activities makes WP1 a crucial component for the overall structure of the BioFairNet project, laying the conceptual, methodological, and participatory foundations necessary for the development of digital tools (WP3), pilot sites (WP4 and WP5), and validation and replicability actions (WP6).

Moreover, the findings of this report contribute to the preparation of the project's first policy brief, Policy Brief 1 (D2.5), enriching the policy-oriented discourse with evidence from regional analyses and sector-specific assessments. By highlighting territorial challenges and opportunities, the report supports the formulation of recommendations that will guide policymakers, industry actors, and civil society stakeholders in facilitating fair and effective transition processes.

In addition, this report provides critical contextual information for the design and deployment of the project's digital pilot, particularly the Mock Up finalized (D3.1), the Green Information Factory (D3.2), and its Evaluation (D3.3). The territorial mapping, conceptual frameworks, and stakeholder insights contained herein underpin the content and functional design of the digital platform, ensuring alignment with regional contexts and sectoral needs.

Finally, the report offers background knowledge relevant to the integration of environmental, economic, and social dimensions into the design of sustainable transition pathways for the pilot regions.

Indeed, in addition to the hotspot regions identified through the environmental and sectoral analysis, the BioFairNet project also considers selected pilot territories characterized by high policy relevance and strong potential for validating and replicating bio-circular transition pathways.

8.1 Pilot 1 Lesvos (Greece)

In addition to its environmental and socio-economic hotspot characteristics, Lesvos represents a relevant pilot region in terms of policy-supported good practices related to sustainable agriculture, biodiversity conservation and community-based transition pathways. A significant example is the implementation of initiatives aimed at promoting sustainable agriculture and agrobiodiversity conservation on the island, supported by international and European cooperation frameworks.

In particular, Lesvos has been the focus of programs promoting sustainable agricultural practices, biodiversity protection and farmer engagement, addressing challenges related to insularity, climate vulnerability and economic marginality (IFR Global). These initiatives explicitly aim to enhance local food systems, protect natural resources and strengthen the resilience of rural communities, aligning with broader EU priorities on sustainable agriculture, biodiversity and inclusive territorial development.

The relevance of Lesvos as a pilot region is further reinforced by the island's exceptionally high level of agricultural biodiversity. Scientific evidence highlights Lesvos as a hotspot of cultivated plant genetic resources, hosting a remarkable diversity of landraces of annual and perennial crops, particularly fruit trees, olives and grapevine. This genetic wealth is the result of long-term farmer selection, adaptation to local pedo-climatic conditions and the persistence of traditional low-input farming systems.

Studies documenting the diversity and conservation status of agricultural plants on Lesvos underline both the ecological and socio-economic value of this agrobiodiversity, as well as the urgent need for integrated strategies combining conservation, sustainable use and value chain development (Douma et al., 2016). Within the BioFairNet framework, Lesvos therefore represents a pilot territory where bio-based and circular transition pathways can build upon existing biodiversity assets, policy initiatives and community-driven practices, offering high potential for learning, validation and replication in other European island and marginal regions.

8.2 Pilot 2 - La Réunion (France – Outermost EU Region)

La Réunion was identified as a pilot region due to its specific territorial, environmental, and socio-economic characteristics, which combine features typical of European regions with constraints commonly observed in non-European contexts. As an outermost region of the European Union, La Réunion is subject to EU regulatory frameworks while facing structural challenges related to geographical isolation, insularity, and high dependence on imported resources.

From an environmental perspective, the region is characterized by limited land availability, pressure on waste management systems, and the need to optimize biomass and organic waste valorization pathways. These challenges are particularly relevant in the context of circular and

bio-based transition strategies, where local resource efficiency and system integration play a critical role.

From a socio-economic standpoint, La Réunion shows a strong dependence on specific value chains, including agriculture, biomass-based activities, and waste-related services, combined with structural vulnerabilities related to employment and market access. These conditions make the region representative of territories where transition processes must carefully balance environmental objectives with social and economic stability.

The identification of La Réunion is directly linked to the implementation activities planned under WP5, where pilot-scale interventions will be developed. This functional connection ensures coherence between the early-stage regional analysis and subsequent pilot activities, supporting the role of La Réunion as a strategic case for assessing place-based and inclusive transition pathways within the BioFairNet project.

In addition to these structural characteristics, La Réunion also represents a relevant reference case in terms of policy-driven good practices supporting bio-circular and climate-resilient transition pathways (Akuo Energy, 2024). A notable example is the long-standing development of agrivoltaic systems on the island, which have been implemented since 2009, making La Réunion one of the earliest European territories to experiment with the integrated production of agricultural outputs and renewable energy under constrained insular conditions.

Reunion Island due to the lack of local fossil fuels, raw materials and land disposal. The use of South African coal was predominant until 2023. It has faced very early to the use of waste in producing renewable and stable energy (production of biogas in the landfills and industrial biogas and CSR incineration plant using half of the domestic waste are developed. Actually, the electric production for the Island mainly comes from Biomass combustion. However, the biomass is actually mainly imported. The actual challenge of La Réunion is to go on the development of green local energy, from its limited resources, by minimizing environmental impacts. The development of circular economy is promoted by the National Agency for Ecological Transition (ADEME) and stakeholders makes Reunion Island one of the most oversea French department implicated in these fields. That's the reason why the development of tools to develop circular economy in agriculture domain can constitute a good lever to accelerate these dynamics.

Over the last fifteen years, agrivoltaics in La Réunion has evolved into a mature ecosystem designed to enhance resilience to extreme weather events such as cyclones, storms and

droughts. Cyclone-proof photovoltaic greenhouses have repeatedly demonstrated their effectiveness in protecting crops during extreme events, while simultaneously optimising land use, water management and energy production. These systems integrate circular practices, including rainwater harvesting and reuse, micro-irrigation systems, and the optimisation of light conditions for crops, contributing to both environmental sustainability and agricultural productivity.

The agrivoltaic model developed in La Réunion has also generated positive socio-economic effects by providing farmers with additional and stable income streams through long-term land-use agreements, while in some cases integrating social innovation components such as agroecological training and rehabilitation programmes. The experience accumulated on the island has progressively been replicated in other European and extra-European territories, confirming its role as a demonstrative good practice with high transferability potential.

8.3 Strategic Insights for Subsequent BioFairNet Activities

The comparative analysis of EU and non-EU hotspot regions highlights strategic considerations relevant for subsequent BioFairNet activities. Hotspot identification emerges from the interaction of environmental pressures, socio-economic dependency on specific value chains, and institutional capacity to support transition processes.

The results of Task 1.1 provide a robust analytical basis for the development of the Sustainable Transition Business Model Framework (D1.2), the co-creation model under Task 1.5, and the design of assessment and digital tools within WP3. The inclusion of non-EU regions strengthens the project's capacity to generate transferable knowledge and supports the overall objective of promoting fair and inclusive green transitions across different territorial contexts.

9. Relation to other projects

The BIO2REG project (Horizon Europe, GA 101135420) provides a complementary conceptual framework for understanding how regions can develop and implement circular and systemic bioeconomy models. Its Regionalisation Concept (Deliverable D1.1, 2025) defines bioeconomy model regions as geographically defined areas where circular bioeconomy principles drive

innovation, sustainable growth, and social well-being by linking regional resources, stakeholders, and strategies in a systemic approach.

The framework identifies key dimensions that are fully consistent with BioFairNet’s regional approach:

- Systemic and multi-level governance, connecting local, regional, and national bioeconomy strategies.
- Stakeholder engagement and co-creation, ensuring participation of policy makers, enterprises, academia, and civil society in regional transition processes.
- Context-specific pathways, recognising that each region’s natural, economic, and social characteristics determine its unique bioeconomy profile.
- Dynamic innovation ecosystems, where regions act as living laboratories that evolve through collaboration, experimentation, and capacity building.

In line with BIO2REG, BioFairNet adopts a territorial approach that treats its pilot regions as bioeconomy transition nodes, enabling testing, co-design, and scaling of circular bio-based solutions. This methodological alignment ensures that BioFairNet contributes to the broader European framework for regional bioeconomy transformation, creating synergies between both projects in stakeholder engagement, capacity building, and regional networking.

The integration of the BIO2REG regionalisation model into BioFairNet strengthens:

- the policy relevance of regional pilots;
- the replicability and scalability of developed models;
- the systemic coherence with EU bioeconomy transition strategies, Smart Specialisation (S3) and the European Green Deal objectives.

In table 3 are resumed the differences between the two projects.

Aspect	BIO2REG Framework	BioFairNet Application
Purpose	Development of systemic bioeconomy model regions	Testing of circular bioeconomy transition approaches in GHG-intensive agricultural and mining areas
Scale	Regional / micro-regional territorial focus	Pilot regions and hotspot-based territorial assessment
Approach	Co-creation with stakeholders; systemic and participatory design	Value-chain demonstration; territorial engagement and sector-specific transition design

Main Outputs	Regionalisation blueprint; methodological and stakeholder guidance	Digital tools, socio-technical transition models, and sectoral insights for fair and circular transition
Synergies	Provides a methodological reference for regional bioeconomy transition pathways	Provides practical validation, use-cases, and transferability evidence for transition models

Table 2 Differences between BIO2REG and BioFairnet

10. Conclusions

The analysis conducted under Task 1.1 confirms that hotspot regions are characterised not only by territorial and sectoral specificities, but also by the structure and functioning of their underlying value chains. Traditional value chains in agriculture and mining remain largely linear and resource-intensive, while emerging bio-circular value chains are developing unevenly across regions, often at limited scale but with significant transition potential.

These findings underline the importance of addressing value chain transformation as a core component of fair and sustainable transitions. The insights generated in this deliverable will directly inform the development of the Sustainable Transition Business Model Framework (D1.2), support co-creation activities with regional stakeholders, and guide the design of digital tools aimed at enabling bio-circular value chain innovation within the BioFairNet project.

References

Scientific literature

- Aguilar-Garrido, A., Paniagua-López, M., Sierra-Aragón, M., Martínez-Garzón, F. J., & Martín-Peinado, F. J. (2023). Remediation potential of mining, agro-industrial, and urban wastes against acid mine drainage. *Scientific Reports*, 13, 39266. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-39266-4>
- Arata, L., Chakrabarti, A., Pahmeyer, C., & Sckokai, P. (2023). Can public policies tackle the phosphorus paradox in pig farming? The case of Po Valley and Lower Saxony. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 415, 137835. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.137835>
- Becker, D., Othmer, F. J., & Greiving, S. (2022). Climate impact assessment for sustainable structural change in the Rhenish lignite mining region. *Land*, 11(7), 957. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11070957>
- Bergamaschi, A., Verma, A., Bhattacharya, A., & Dell'Acqua, F. (2025). Joint analysis of optical and SAR vegetation indices for vineyard monitoring: Assessing biomass dynamics and phenological stages over Po Valley, Italy. *arXiv preprint*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.13327>;
- Blondet, I., Schreck, E., Viers, J., et al. (2019). Atmospheric dust characterisation in the mining district of Cartagena–La Unión, Spain: Air quality and health risks assessment. *Science of the Total Environment*, 693, 133020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.133020>
- Bonaldo, D., Bellafiore, D., Ferrarin, C., Ferretti, R., Ricchi, A., Sangelantoni, L., & Vitelletti, M. L. (2023). The summer 2022 drought: A taste of future climate for the Po Valley (Italy)? *Regional Environmental Change*, 23(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-022-02004-z>
- Brodny, J., & Tutak, M. (2020). The use of artificial neural networks to analyze greenhouse gas and air pollutant emissions from the mining and quarrying sector in the European Union. *Energies*, 13(8), 1925. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13081925>
- Cáceres, L. M., Ruiz, F., Bermejo, J., Fernández, L., González Regalado, M. L., Vidal, J. R., Abad, M., Izquierdo, T., Toscano, A., Gómez, P., & Romero, V. (2023). Sediments as sentinels of pollution episodes in the middle estuary of the Tinto River (SW Spain). *Soil Systems*, 7(4), 95. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soilsystems7040095>
- Caparrós Martínez, J. L., García, J. M., Rueda López, N., & de Pablo Valenciano, J. (2020). Mapping green infrastructure and socioeconomic indicators as a public management tool: The case of the municipalities of Andalusia (Spain). *Environmental Sciences Europe*, 32(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-020-00375-8>
- Caparrós Martínez, J. L., Rueda López, N., & Rodríguez Fernández, J. L. (2020). Sustainability challenges in Andalusia's energy and industrial systems. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 268, 122151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.122151>

- Colombo, L., Marongiu, A., Malvestiti, G., Fossati, G., ... & Lanzani, G. G. (2023). Assessing the impacts and feasibility of emissions reduction scenarios in the Po Valley. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 11, 1240816. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2023.1240816>
- Cozma, P., Bețianu, C., Hlihor, R.-M., Simion, I. M., & Gavrilăscu, M. (2024). Bio recovery of metals through biomining within circularity-based solutions. *Processes*, 12(9), 1793. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr12091793>
- Dahmen, D. (2025). Future residual lakes in the Rhenish lignite mining area – Geotechnical challenges and special aspects. In Wichtmann, T., Machaček, J., & Tafili, M. (Eds.), *Recent developments of soil mechanics and geotechnics in theory and practice* (pp. 17–34). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-71896-0_2
- Dang, R., Jacob, D. J., Zhai, S., Yang, L. H., ... & Liao, H. (2024). A satellite-based indicator for diagnosing particulate nitrate sensitivity to precursor emissions. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 58. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.4c08082>
- Delplace, G., Schreck, E., Pokrovsky, O. S., et al. (2020). Accumulation of heavy metals in phytoliths from reeds growing on mining environments in Southern Europe. *Science of the Total Environment*, 712, 135595. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.135595>
- Deshaies, M. (2020). Metamorphosis of mining landscapes in the Lower Lusatian lignite basin (Germany): New uses and new image of a mining region. *Les Cahiers de la recherche architecturale urbaine et paysagère*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.4000/craup.4018>
- Douma, A., Koutis, K., Thanopoulos, R., Tsigou, R., Galanidis, A., & Bebeli, P. J. (2016). Diversity of agricultural plants on Lesbos Island (Northeast Aegean, Greece) with emphasis on fruit trees. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 210, 65–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2016.07.009>
- Fernández-Lobato, L., Guzmán, G. I., Soto, D., & Infante-Amate, J. (2024). Environmental impact of the most representative Spanish olive oil farming systems: A life cycle assessment study. *Science of the Total Environment*, 917, 168400. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.168400>
- Gerwin, W., Raab, T., Birkhofer, K., et al. (2023). Perspectives of lignite post-mining landscapes under changing environmental conditions: What can we learn from a comparison between the Rhenish and Lusatian region in Germany? *Environmental Sciences Europe*, 35(36). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-023-00738-z>
- Greiving, S., Gruehn, D., & Reicher, C. (2022). The Rhenish coal-mining area—Assessing the transformational talents and challenges of a region in fundamental structural change. *Land*, 11(6), 826. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11060826>
- Hachem, F., Palazzi, E., Cadoux, R., Soteras, I. S., Zaccarelli, N., & Orecchini, F. (2024). GIS mapping of agricultural plastic waste in southern Europe. *Science of the Total Environment*, 916, 168267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.168267>
- Hamam, M., Chinnici, G., Di Vita, G., Pappalardo, G., Pecorino, B., Maesano, G., & D’Amico, M. (2021). Circular economy models in agro-food systems: A review. *Sustainability*, 13(6), 3453. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13063453>

- Küster, A., Wilking, J., & Mittmann, A. (2023). Mining law and water management challenges as a result of the coal phase-out. *Mining Report*, 159(6), 535–542.
- Leuchner, M., Hinrichs, F., Roß-Nickoll, M., & Letmathe, P. (2024). Ecosystem services as a framework for transformation of the Rhenish mining area. In *Transformation towards sustainability: A novel interdisciplinary framework from RWTH Aachen University* (pp. 233–270). Springer.
- Luís, A. T., Fortes, J. C., Santisteban, M., Dávila, J. M., Caraballo, M. A., Terrones Saeta, J. M., Díaz Curiel, J., & Grande, J. A. (2024). Relationships between hydrogeochemistry and diatoms in acid mine drainage affected media: The case of the Iberian Pyrite Belt; functioning models for an all metallogenetic province. *Journal of Geochemical Exploration*, 284, 107537. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gexplo.2024.107537>
- Martinez, P., & Blanco, M. (2019). Sensitivity of agricultural development to water-related drivers: The case of Andalusia (Spain). *Water*, 11(9), 1854. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w11091854>
- Montanari, A., Nguyen, H., Rubinetti, S., Ceola, S., Galelli, S., Rubino, A., & Zanchettin, D. (2023). Why the 2022 Po River drought is the worst in the past two centuries. *Science Advances*, 9(32), eadg8304. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adg8304>
- Monteleone, B., & Borzì, I. (2024). Drought in the Po Valley: Identification, impacts and strategies to manage the events. *Water*, 16(8), 1187. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w16081187>
- Morellón, M., Morales Molino, C., Vegas, J., Vicente de Vera, A., Plà Trabes, S., Leunda, M., Sánchez España, J., Rodríguez, J. A., Arroyo, X., & Mata, M. P. (2025). Reconstructing the environmental impact of mining on mountain lakes. *Science of the Total Environment*, 961, 178382. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2025.178382>
- Peco, J. D., Thouin, H., Esbrí, J. M., Campos Rodríguez, H. R., García Noguero, E. M., Breeze, D., Villena, J., Gloaguen, E., Higuera, P. L., & Battaglia Brunet, F. (2023). Mobility of antimony in contrasting surface environments of a mine site: Influence of redox conditions and microbial communities. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30(48), 29734–29746. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-29734-9>
- Perni, Á., & Martínez Paz, J. M. (2023). Socioeconomic assessment of the restoration of highly modified coastal ecosystems by mining activities. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 103, 107251. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2023.107251>
- Pivato, A., Pegoraro, L., Masiol, M., Bortolazzo, E., Bonato, T., Formenton, G., Cappai, G., Beggio, G., & Arboretti Giancristofaro, R. (2023). Long time series analysis of air quality data in the Veneto region (Northern Italy) to support environmental policies. *Atmospheric Environment*, 298, 119610. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2023.119610>
- Ponti, L., Cossu, Q. A., & Gutierrez, A. P. (2024). Impact of climate change on the potential distribution and abundance of the olive fly (*Bactrocera oleae*) in the Mediterranean Basin. *Science of the Total Environment*, 921, 168708. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.168708>

- Radtke, J., & David, M. (2024). How Germany is phasing out lignite: Insights from the Coal Commission and local communities. *Energy, Sustainability and Society*, 14(7). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13705-023-00434-z>
- Renna, S., Lunghi, J., Granella, F., Malpede, M., & Di Simine, D. (2024). Impacts of agriculture on PM10 pollution and human health in the Lombardy region in Italy. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 12, 1369678. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2024.1369678>
- Rey, P. J., Cañadas, E. M., Alcántara, J. M., & Manzaneda, A. J. (2019). Landscape-moderated biodiversity effects of ground herb cover in olive groves: Implications for management and policy. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 277, 61–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2019.03.011>
- Romero Macías, E. M., & Terrones Saeta, J. M. (2024). Dinamización turística de la comarca minera de Tharsis (Huelva, España). *Pasos: Revista de Turismo y Patrimonio Cultural*, 22(2), 305–322. <https://doi.org/10.25145/j.pasos.2024.22.021>
- Ruiz Cánovas, C. R., Basallote, M. D., & Macías, F. (2020). Distribution and availability of rare earth elements and trace elements in the estuarine waters of the Ría of Huelva (SW Spain). *Environmental Pollution*, 267, 115506. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.115506>
- Sánchez de la Campa, A. M., Sánchez-Rodas, D., Márquez, G., & Romero, E. (2020). 2009–2017 trends of PM10 in the legendary Riotinto mining district of SW Spain. *Atmospheric Research*, 238, 104878. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosres.2020.104878>
- Schoonhoven, Y., & Runhaar, H. (2018). Conditions for the adoption of agro-ecological farming practices: A holistic framework illustrated with the case of almond farming in Andalusia. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 84, 39–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2018.02.003>
- Scotto, F., Bacco, D., Lasagni, S., Trentini, A., Poluzzi, V., & Vecchi, R. (2021). A multi-year source apportionment of PM2.5 at multiple sites in the southern Po Valley (Italy). *Atmospheric Pollution Research*, 12(6), 101101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apr.2021.101101>
- Soana, E., Gervasio, M. P., Granata, T., Colombo, D., & Castaldelli, G. (2024). Climate change impacts on eutrophication in the Po River (Italy): Temperature-mediated reduction in nitrogen export but no effect on phosphorus. *Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 143, 148–163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jes.2023.07.008>
- Soltero, V. M., Rincón, L., Callejón-Ferre, Á. J., & Manzano-Agugliaro, F. (2020). Sustainable biomass pellets from olive grove residues: Development in Andalusia (Spain). *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 276, 123233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123233>
- Straffelini, E., & Tarolli, P. (2023). Climate change-induced aridity is affecting agriculture in Northeast Italy. *Agricultural Systems*, 208, 103647. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2023.103647>
- Viers, J., Freydier, R., Grande, J. A., Zouiten, C., et al. (2023). The use of copper isotopes for understanding metal transfer mechanisms within the continuum mine–river–dam (Huelva Region, Spain). *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30(18), 25802–25816. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-25802-2>

- Aguilar-Garrido, A., Paniagua-López, M., Sierra-Aragón, M., et al. (2023). Remediation potential of mining, agro-industrial, and urban wastes against acid mine drainage. *Scientific Reports*, 13, 12120. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-39266-4>
- D’Adamo, I., Gastaldi, M., Morone, P., Rosa, P., Sassanelli, C., Settembre-Blundo, D., & Shen, Y. (2022). Bioeconomy of sustainability: Drivers, opportunities and policy implications. *Sustainability*, 14, 200. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14010200>
- Eliasson, A., Borzacchiello, M. T., Camia, A., Girardi, I., & Spartico, G. (2025). *National bioeconomy strategies in Europe: State of play September 2025* (JRC143845). European Commission, Joint Research Centre. <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC143845>
- European Commission. (2025, November 27). *A strategic framework for a competitive and sustainable EU bioeconomy* (COM(2025) 960 final). EUR-Lex. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52025DC0960>
- Fava, F., Gardossi, L., Brigidi, P., Morone, P., Carosi, D. A. R., & Lenzi, A. (2021). The bioeconomy in Italy and the new national strategy for a more competitive and sustainable country. *New Biotechnology*, 61, 124–136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbt.2020.11.009>
- Ferreira, V., Pié, L., Mainar-Causapé, A., et al. (2024). The bioeconomy in Spain as a new economic paradigm: The role of key sectors with different approaches. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 26, 3369–3393. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-022-02830-5>
- Gruppo di Coordinamento Nazionale per la Bioeconomia (GCNB). (2024, 16 dicembre). *Piano d’azione aggiornato (2025–2027) per l’implementazione della Strategia italiana per la bioeconomia BIT II* (Versione aggiornata). Presidenza del Consiglio dei Ministri – CNBBSV.
- Hilgert, P., Stark, S., von Cossel, M., Lewandowski, I., Schurr, U., & Venghaus, S. (2025). Monitoring the bioeconomy transformation potential for Germany's largest lignite mining region: The Rheinische Revier. *EFB Bioeconomy Journal*, 5, 100074. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioeco.2024.100074>
- Liobikienė, G., & Miceikienė, A. (2023). Contribution of the European Bioeconomy Strategy to the Green Deal policy: Challenges and opportunities in implementing these policies. *Sustainability*, 15, 7139. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15097139>

Lühmann, M., & Vogelpohl, T. (2023). The bioeconomy in Germany: A failing political project? *Ecological Economics*, 207, 107783. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2023.107783>

Sayadi Gmada, S., Cátedra, M., Capote, C., Parra-López, C., García, M., Ronchel, C., Dueñas-Sánchez, R., Ortiz, E., Argüelles, M., & Cruz, J. L. (2025). Driving sustainability: Circular bioeconomy and governance in Andalusia (Southern Spain). *Sustainability*, 17, 3128. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17073128>

Schurr, U., & Slusarczyk, H. (2022). Bioeconomy in North Rhine-Westphalia. In D. Thrän & U. Moesenfechtel (Eds.), *The bioeconomy system*. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-64415-7_12

Stegmann, P., Londo, M., & Junginger, M. (2020). The circular bioeconomy: Its elements and role in European bioeconomy clusters. *Resources, Conservation & Recycling: X*, 6, 100029. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcrx.2019.100029>

Grey literature

Agriconsulting Supporto Istituzionale S.r.l. (2023, March). (Fear) Rapporto Annuale Di Valutazione AI 2022. ministero dell'agricoltura della sovranità alimentare e delle foreste. (<https://www.reterurale.it/flex/cm/pages/ServeBLOB.php/L/IT/IDPagina/24806>);

Akuo Energy. (2024, February 7). Agrivoltaics: 15 years of experience in Reunion have led to the creation of a segment establishing itself across Europe [Press release]. <https://www.akuoenergy.com/en/press/agrivoltaics-15-years-experience-reunion-have-led-creation-segment-establishing-itself-europe>;

ARPA Lombardia. (2024). INEMAR – Inventario emissioni in atmosfera, edizione 2021. <https://www.arpalombardia.it/temi-ambientali/aria/inventario/inventario-delle-emissioni/> e database;

ARPA Lombardia. Rete di rilevamento qualità dell'aria (RRQA). (<https://www.arpalombardia.it/temi-ambientali/aria/rete-di-rilevamento>);

BDN-Banca Dati Nazionale Anagrafe Zootechnica. Statistiche. (https://www.vetinfo.it/j6_statistiche/);

BioökonomieREVIER. (2025). *A region heading towards bioeconomy*. Forschungszentrum Jülich/BioökonomieREVIER. Retrieved November 17, 2025;

Buckwell, A. Nordang Uhre, A. Williams, J. Poláková, W. Blum, J. Schiefer, G. J. Lair, A. Heissenhuber, P. Schießl, C. Krämer and W. Habe, *The sustainable intensification of European Agriculture*, RISE Foundation, 2014;

Cross-cutting story 4: Nutrients, European Environmental Agency, 2025 (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/publications/zero-pollution/cross-cutting-stories/cross-cutting-stories>);

Directorate-General for Energy. (2020, October). Regional Development Agency Rhenish Lignite Mining Area Case study. European Commission (https://energy.ec.europa.eu/publications/regional-development-agency-rhenish-lignite-mining-area_en);

Directorate-General for Internal Policies. (2016). Research for AGRI Committee - Agriculture in Andalusia. European Parliament;

EEA (European Environment Agency). European city air quality viewer (375 cities). (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/topics/in-depth/air-pollution/european-city-air-quality-viewer/european-city-air-quality-viewer>);

Enhancing Regional Mining Ecosystems in the European Union: Securing the Green Transition and Supply of Mineral Raw Materials, OECD Rural Studies, OECD Publishing, Paris OECD (2025) (https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/enhancing-regional-mining-ecosystems-in-the-european-union_97ba1224-en.html);

ERSAF Lombardia. (2022). Osservatorio Suini 2021–2022 (<https://www.ersaf.lombardia.it/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/OSSERVATORIO-SUINI-2022.pdf> e Osservatorio Suini 2020–2021: <https://www.ersaf.lombardia.it/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/OSSERVATORIO-SUINI-2021.pdf>);

European Commission. (2025, March). *Agriculture statistics at regional level - Statistics Explained-Eurostat*. Eurostat;

Eutrophication caused by atmospheric nitrogen deposition in Europe, European Environmental Agency, 2024 (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/indicators/eutrophication-caused-by-atmospheric-nitrogen>);

IFR Global. (n.d.). Greece: Lesvos Sustainable Agriculture & Biodiversity. Retrieved January 31, 2026, from <https://ifrglobal.org/program/greece-lesvos-sustainable-agriculture-biodiversity>;

Investment Monitor. (2023). How Montréal's agtech community is boosting local food production. How Montréal's agtech community is boosting local food production

Montréal International. (2023). Greater Montréal's agtech sector serving sustainable agriculture. Greater Montréal's agtech sector serving sustainable agriculture – Montréal International

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2025). *Enhancing regional mining ecosystems in Andalusia, Spain* (OECD Regional Development Papers). (https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2025/06/enhancing-regional-mining-ecosystems-in-andalusia-spain_2bb58312/fe82bdff-en.pdf);

Perez, I. (2025, October 10). *Spain: Participatory water governance - A new model for regional cap implementation?* Agricultural and Rural Convention EU;

Policies for the Future of Farming and Food in Spain, OECD Agriculture and Food Policy Reviews, OECD Publishing, Paris, 2023 (https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/policies-for-the-future-of-farming-and-food-in-spain_a93d26be-en.html);

Soil pollution and ecosystems, European Environmental Agency, 2025 (https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/publications/zero-pollution/ecosystems/soil-pollution-and-ecosystems?utm_source);

T. Monen, S. Kivinen, J. M. Kotilainen, J. Leino, *Social and environmental impacts of mining activities in the EU*, 2022.

Université de Montréal / INRS. (2023). Using genomics to reduce the carbon footprint of the agri-food industry. Using genomics to reduce the carbon footprint of the agri-food industry – UdeM Nouvelles

WHO. (2021). Global Air Quality Guidelines (PM2.5, PM10, NO₂, O₃, SO₂, CO). <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240034228>

Institutional sources and datasets

ACUAMED. IDAM Campo de Dalías – ficha técnica (30→40 hm³/año; destino y consumos). <https://www.acuamed.es/instalaciones/desaladoras/campo-de-dalias>;

ACUAMED. IDAM Carboneras – ficha técnica (~42 hm³/año). <https://www.acuamed.es/instalaciones/desaladoras/carboneras>;

BOE – Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica. (2019). Declaración de impacto ambiental: Planta fotovoltaica vinculada a la desaladora de Campo de Dalías;

EEA. (2024). European city air quality viewer (per benchmark PM2.5 europeo). (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/topics/in-depth/air-pollution/european-city-air-quality-viewer>);

European Commission. (2021). The Just Transition Mechanism: Making sure no one is left behind. Publications Office of the European Union;

European Commission. (2023). Raw Materials Scoreboard 2023. Publications Office of the European Union;

European Commission. (2024a). EU Industrial Strategy Progress Report 2024. Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs;

European Commission. (2024b). European Green Deal and Zero Pollution Action Plan: Progress assessment. Publications Office of the European Union;

European Environment Agency (EEA). (2023). Zero Pollution Monitoring and Outlook 2025. EEA Report No. 14/2023;

- Eurostat. (2024). Regional Economic and Environmental Accounts (NUTS2–NUTS3 datasets). European Union;
- Gajdzik, B., Tobór-Osadnik, K., Wolniak, R., & Grebski, W. W. (2024). European climate policy in the context of the problem of methane emissions from coal mines in Poland. *Energies*, 17(10), 2396 (<https://doi.org/10.3390/en17102396>);
- IECA (Instituto de Estadística y Cartografía de Andalucía). Indicadores ambientales (NH₃, etc.). (<https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/institutodeestadisticaycartografia>);
- Joint Research Centre (JRC). (2022). Indicators for the EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System. Publications Office of the European Union;
- Junta de Andalucía – Consejería de Sostenibilidad, Medio Ambiente y Economía Azul. (2022–2027). Plan Hidrológico de las Cuencas Mediterráneas Andaluzas (PHCMA). Anejo 9 – Inventario de recursos (incl. desalación);
- Junta de Andalucía. (2022). Plan Especial de Sequía – Cuencas Mediterráneas Andaluzas. (<https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/portal/portal/web/guest/temas/agua/gestion-sequias>);
- Junta de Andalucía. (2022–2027). Programa de Medidas – PHCMA. (<https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/portal/portal/web/guest/temas/agua/pla-nificacion-hidrologica>);
- Manowska, A., Tobór-Osadnik, K., & Wyganowska, M. (2017). Economic and social aspects of restructuring Polish coal mining: Focusing on Poland and the EU. *Resources Policy*, 52, 192–200 (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2017.02.006>);
- PIREC 2030 (Plan Integral de Residuos de Andalucía). Marco para residuos agrarios y agroplásticos (<https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/portal/portal/web/guest/temas/residuos-y-economia-circular/planificacion>);
- REDIAM – Cartografía oficial de invernaderos (Andalucía). Visor/series de cobertura. (<https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/site/rediam> (buscar “Cartografía de Invernaderos”));

Annex 1 - Stakeholder Engagement Plan for Engagement and Community Data Collection Strategy

Lead Partner: UNIVERSITY OF FERRARA

Author(s): Asia Guerreschi

Project details			
Project name	Bioeconomy and Circular Economy Fair Network Digitally fair and accessible network for reducing GHG activities with circular and bio-economy models		
Project acronym	BioFairNet	Start/Duration	January 1 st , 2025 (48 months)
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2024-Circ Bio-01-7	Call identifier	HORIZON-CL6-2024-CIRCBIO-01
Type of Action	HORIZON-IA	Coordinator	UNIVERSITY OF NAPLES FEDERICO II
Contact person	Marina Albanese (Project Coordinator) - biofairnet@unina.it		
Project website	www.biofairnetproject.eu		

Deliverable details			
Deliverable name	Stakeholder Engagement Plan inserted in D.1.1 for the completion of D.1.2 results		
Number	D1.1	Work package	WP1
Dissemination level	Public	Nature	Report
Due date (M)	January 2026	Submission date (M)	31/1/26
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Reviewer(s)	QAC and EC	On 5/09/2025, BioFairNet QAC and EC was asked to provide SEP feedback. The members who contributed are listed in the following rows.		
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Reviewer n°2	Salome R. A. Bukachi	QAC and EC Committee Member		By request to the coordinator UNIVERSITY OF NAPLES FEDERICO II

				(see information above).
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Reviewer n°3	Nikolaos Ntavos	QAC and EC Committee Member		By request to the coordinator UNIVERSITY OF NAPLES FEDERICO II (see information above).
Reviewer n°4	Christian Chiavetta	QAC and EC Committee Member		By request to the coordinator UNIVERSITY OF NAPLES FEDERICO II (see information above).
Final review & quality approval	30 October, 2025			

Document History			
Date	Version	Name	Changes
25/08/2025	1	SEP_V01	N/A
5/09/2025	2	SEP_V02	Main changes: 1) A Gantt Chart was added; 2) IAP2 section was shifted in an earlier section; 3) SSG suggested carrying out interviews before the workshops, therefore, a mention was added.
30/10/2025	3	SEP_V03_FINAL	Last few additions alongside some syntax revisions: 1) structure of the SEP; 2) addition of a language of the survey.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
WP	Work Package
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
SEP	Stakeholder Engagement Plan
UNINA	Università Federico II
UNIFE	Università degli Studi di Ferrara
UNITELMA	Unitelma Sapienza University of Rome
BAY	Bayreuth University
UNITRENTO	University of Trento
SATEC	S istemas A vanzados de T ecnología S.A. (SATEC)
CERTH	Centre for Research and Technology, Hellas Institute for Bio-economy and Agri-technology
Ecoimagination	Ecoimagination
UNA	University of the Aegean
UniCologne	University of Cologne (Universität zu Köln)
SSG	Sustainability Solutions Group
CUK	The Cooperative University of Kenya
UNR	Reunion Island University

Executive Summary

This Stakeholder Engagement Plan (SEP) is developed as part of Deliverable D.1.1 of the BioFairNet project (contract no. 101181568). It sets out the framework, objectives, and methodology for engaging stakeholders in the agricultural and mining sectors across selected European and non-European regions, in order to support the transition of greenhouse gas-intensive regions towards sustainable, bio-circular economies. The SEP is a key element for the successful implementation of stakeholders in the sectors of interest in the development of a co-creation model.

The purpose of the SEP is twofold. First, it provides a structured approach for identifying, involving, and interacting with stakeholders in Spain (Andalucía – Iberian Pyrite Belt, greenhouse and monoculture agriculture), Germany (Rhenish Lignite District), Italy (Po Valley agricultural subregions), as well as Greece, La Réunion, Canada, and Kenya. These areas represent both sectoral diversity and geographic breadth, ensuring that the project captures a wide range of perspectives. Second, the SEP ensures that stakeholder input is systematically integrated into the project, particularly into the design of the co-creation model due in M18, thereby aligning BioFairNet’s outputs with the realities and needs of affected communities and industry actors.

The SEP is structured around a phased engagement strategy. In the initial phase, beginning in September 2025 (M8), all partners will collect and consolidate stakeholder contacts into a shared database. Between September and November 2025 (M9–M11), a questionnaire will be distributed in Italian, Spanish, and German, designed to capture information on digital requirements for the BioFairNet platform and to identify the main barriers and drivers for the adoption of circular and bioeconomy strategies. The results will provide a baseline for designing sector-specific workshops in M14.

These workshops will be conducted in local languages, with dedicated sessions for agricultural and mining stakeholders. An in-person workshop in Kenya will ensure inclusivity for communities with limited digital access. In M17, two cross-regional workshops in English

will bring together English-speaking stakeholders, enabling a comparative and transnational exchange of perspectives.

The engagement strategy is guided by principles of inclusivity, transparency, participation, adaptability, and accountability. Special attention is given to linguistic accessibility, the inclusion of vulnerable or underrepresented groups, and the provision of clear feedback to stakeholders on how their contributions are used. Engagement techniques include desk-based stakeholder mapping, questionnaires, participatory workshops, and systematic follow-up communication. Monitoring and evaluation mechanisms ensure that engagement activities are representative, effective, and aligned with BioFairNet's objectives, with regular feedback loops through the Quality Assurance Committee (QAC) and Ethics Committee (EC) in M9 and M17.

By the end of M18, the Stakeholder Engagement Platform (SEP) will have gathered valuable insights that will directly inform two key areas: (i) The co-creation model and Deliverable

D.1.2 within Work Package (WP) 1, and (ii) the questionnaire for the Green Information Factory in WP3.

Beyond any WP, these results will inform subsequent work packages, guiding pilot activities, digital platform development, and cross-regional analyses. In this way, the SEP provides not only a roadmap for engagement but also a foundation for ensuring that BioFairNet delivers meaningful, equitable, and actionable outcomes for the transition to a fair bio-circular economy.

1. Introduction

To collect information necessary to complete D.1.2 for WP1 and map the stakeholders focuses on establishing a robust foundation for stakeholder collaboration in the transition of greenhouse gas (GHG)-intensive regions toward sustainable, bio-circular economies.

The first stage of the project (currently M8-9) integrates the results of WP1 and WP2 that define the stakeholders in cooperation with the consortium's feedback and the Green Information Factory (WP3). The latter process supports designating the framework to collect perceptions and uses regarding digital matters for project objectives that will be validated in WP6.

To summarise, WP1 integrates research, analysis, and direct engagement with stakeholders in both the agricultural and mining sectors, across selected European and non-European regions. The scope of WP1 spans several interlinked tasks. Task 1.1 conducted in-depth research to identify hotspots in three EU regions focusing on both traditional and bio-circular value chains.

This engagement plan outlines how the plan wants to identify, involve, and interact with relevant stakeholders from the hotspots identified by Task 1.1 (UNINA) which are: Spain (Andalucía – Iberian Pyrite Belt, greenhouse/monoculture agriculture), Germany (Rhenish Lignite District), Italy (Po Valley agricultural subregions), and to make it coherent with the rest of the project and partners we included Greece, La Réunion, Canada, and Kenya. These areas represent both sectoral diversity and geographic breadth, ensuring the project captures a range of challenges and opportunities in bio-circular transformation.

1.1 Purpose of the document

The aim is to identify challenges to the implementation of the final BioFairNet product (ie. digital divide) and the barriers and drivers to the transition to bio and circular strategies from the stakeholders of the two identified sectors.

1.2 Structure of the document

The document is structured to guide the reader through the rationale, methods, and planned activities of stakeholder engagement, especially direct to complete the co-creation model due M18 that will serve as a baseline for the stakeholder analysis for the project. Following the introduction, the background section situates the SEP within the wider objectives of BioFairNet and highlights the regions and sectors of focus.

The community engagement chapter presents the guiding principles, identifies the types of stakeholders involved, and describes the main engagement tools, namely the questionnaire and workshops, alongside the monitoring and evaluation framework. The strategies section then outlines the key deadlines, responsibilities, and technical implementation steps that will ensure the engagement process is coherent, inclusive, and effective.

1.3 Relation to other project deliverables / tasks / consortium feedback

This stakeholder engagement plan (SEP) looks to collect information from also WP2 with input from the pilot (WP 4 and 5) and the input of non-EU partners (SSG and CUK) from Canada and Kenya to map the stakeholders who are to benefit from the results of BioFairNet.

2. Background

This SEP is a guide for how the project team will work together. It outlines the purpose, engagement objectives and techniques, and roles and responsibilities of the engagement and data collection portion of the questionnaire, workshops, that provide feedback necessary to the perception collection and the co-Creation model due in M18.

2.1 Study Description

The project aims to accelerate the transition of greenhouse gas-intensive regions in the **agricultural and mining sectors** towards sustainable, bio-circular economies by combining research, stakeholder engagement, and co-creation. Within this framework, WP1 and WP2

provide the foundation for understanding regional hotspots, analysing business models, and building participatory processes with stakeholders from the agricultural and mining sectors.

SEP supports engaging with stakeholders to identify barriers, drivers, and digital requirements (with WP3) that influence the uptake of bio- and circular economy strategies to build a digital product (the final aim of BioFairNet) using a preliminary questionnaire (M9-M11) and workshops (M14) to build the (co-created) model due M18 that will give the foundation for the rest of the project.

The first phase of the study will focus on identifying and contacting stakeholders from these regions, building a comprehensive database that covers both direct value-chain actors and related community stakeholders. It will then deploy a structured questionnaire, gathering information on the digital needs of stakeholders for the platform, as well as the main circular and bioeconomy challenges they face. The results of this questionnaire will be analysed and used to design a series of regional workshops, which will take place in month fourteen of the project.

To reduce at most the limitations regarding digital divide, gender representation, and inclusion, the consortium has aimed to: 1) contact people personally with multiple reminders by ECO; 2) semi-structured interviews led by UniCologne to go deeper to any detail that might be left unanswered; 3) contacting sectoral representatives (ie. consortia) to integrate any stakeholder who was not contacted directly from the main list initially collected.

The second phase of the study will use workshops to deepen the understanding of stakeholder perspectives and co-develop strategies for overcoming barriers to the bio-circular transition. These workshops will be held in local languages (Italian, Spanish, and German) and in English for cross-regional exchanges, including an in-person session in Kenya. They will provide opportunities for dialogue between agricultural and mining stakeholders, community representatives, and technology and policy actors.

These results will not only map the main actors in the targeted regions but also provide an initial overview of their priorities, challenges, and expectations regarding the transition to

bio-circular systems. In doing so, it will guide partners in designing effective and equitable interventions that align with the needs of industry actors, policymakers, civil society organisations, and local communities.

The engagement process builds upon the hotspot identification work carried out under Task 1.1. The selected areas include the Iberian Pyrite Belt and agricultural monocultures in Andalucía (Spain), the Rhenish Lignite District (Germany), and the Po Valley (Italy). To reflect the breadth of the consortium and ensure inclusivity, the scope also extends to Greece, specifically with attention to agricultural (olive oil production) in the area of Lesvos and mining (lignite) sector in the area of Western Macedonia as identified by CERTH, La Réunion, Canada, and Kenya. These regions represent both sectoral diversity and geographic spread, making it possible to compare challenges across contexts with different economic and social structures. A further description of how the hotspots were selected is presented in DL1.1.

The engagement process aims to generate actionable insights into both the technological and social dimensions of transition. The results will be incorporated into the co-creation model developed in Task 1.5, which will combine research and stakeholder knowledge to deliver practical recommendations. In addition to informing WP1 deliverables, the findings of this study may contribute to subsequent work packages, guiding pilot activities, digital platform development, and comparative analysis. In this way, the study will not only serve WP1 but also strengthen the coherence and impact of the project as a whole.

2.2 Engagement

In the preliminary step, UNIFE and UNITRENTO gathered from the data collected from Task 1.1 (hotspots) to identify the outcomes that the stakeholders mentioned and studied. This provided the space to collect information on the type of stakeholder that should be contacted.

2.3 Guiding Principles

Guiding Principles are designed to ensure that engagement and data collection activities help to inform the study by identifying and considering the study's impacts on interested and

affected parties, including providing equity considerations for vulnerable and underrepresented communities. As noted above, the impacts of participating in an engagement/ data collection activity must also be considered, especially when working with vulnerable populations or in consideration of digital divide circumstances.

The stakeholder engagement activities of BioFairNet are guided by a set of principles that ensure consistency, inclusivity, and transparency across all regions and sectors. These principles provide the framework for interactions with agricultural and mining stakeholders in Europe and beyond, and they guarantee that the knowledge and experiences collected during the engagement process contribute meaningfully to the project's objectives.

First, the engagement process is built on **inclusivity and representation**. Stakeholders are identified and invited to participate not only based on their institutional or industrial role but also with the intention of capturing the diversity of perspectives within the agricultural and mining value chains. This includes producers, workers, cooperatives, business associations, research institutions, and civil society actors, as well as representatives of vulnerable or marginalised groups where relevant. In line with the project's transnational nature, linguistic accessibility is prioritised, and all online communications include instructions in Italian, French, Greek, German, and Spanish on how to translate content into their preferred language.

Second, the engagement is conducted based on the **principle of transparency and trust-building**. All stakeholders are clearly informed of the scope of the engagement, the type of information being collected, and the ways in which their contributions will be used. Particular care is taken not to create unrealistic expectations, especially in regions where communities are directly exposed to the social and environmental impacts of agricultural or mining activities. This means that the engagement process is explicitly framed as a channel for information gathering and co-design within the project, not as a mechanism for direct financial or policy commitments.

Third, the process follows a **principle of participation and co-creation**. Stakeholders are not treated as passive data providers but as active contributors whose perspectives help shape the questionnaire, inform the design of workshops, and validate the outputs of WP1. The

workshops expressed in the following sections, both regional and cross-regional, are therefore conceived not only as moments of consultation but as spaces for collaborative dialogue, where participants can compare experiences, identify common challenges, and explore potential solutions.

A fourth principle is adaptability to local contexts. The agricultural and mining sectors vary widely across the targeted regions, from the greenhouse production systems of Andalucía to the lignite mining operations in the Rhenish district, and from the intensive livestock systems of the Po Valley to the in-person engagement planned in Kenya. The engagement approach is therefore flexible, adapting formats, languages, and facilitation methods to the specific needs of each region. This also includes recognition of cultural and territorial specificities, which are integrated into the design of the co-creation model in Task 1.5.

Finally, the process is underpinned by feedback and accountability. Participants in both the questionnaire and workshops receive concise summaries of how their inputs have been used, thereby ensuring that their engagement produces tangible recognition. This feedback loop strengthens the credibility of the project and supports the establishment of long-term relationships with stakeholders who may continue to be involved in later phases of the project. Together, these guiding principles provide a coherent framework for stakeholder engagement that is respectful, collaborative, and results-oriented. They ensure that BIOFAIRNET not only collects valuable information but also builds a foundation of trust and shared understanding that will strengthen the impact of the project's outcomes.

The public processes of engagement should:

- Suggest that populations represented by this study's findings should be involved in future decision-making processes resulting from this study.
- Promote sustainable decisions by recognizing and communicating the needs and interests of all participants, including decision-makers.
- Seek out and facilitate the involvement of those potentially affected by or interested in decisions resulting from the study.

- Seek input from participants in designing how they participate.
- Provide participants with the information they need to participate in a meaningful way.
- Ensure that the participants contribution and participation is voluntary and from an informed perspective. They can choose to drop off from the process without any negative dire consequences on them.
- Communicate to participants how their input affected the study.

Therefore, the practical principles will work towards:

- Clear introductions and information provided in all communications;
- Possibility for stakeholders contacted to include other parties (adequate to the study) at all times to extend the network;
- Updates after each activity (questionnaire, workshop, and results from the co-creation model);
- Updates throughout the following deliverables and project achievements. To avoid potential excessive contact, this will be limited to updates with the possibility for stakeholders to reach out to the Project Coordinator;
- Possibility to translate all communications into their language using technology (ie. browser);
- Provide alternatives to digital communication (ie. in person workshops where possible) or use larger networks for specific communications (ie. sectoral consortia);
- Monitor mechanisms, such as the questionnaire and workshop framework sent for feedback to the Quality Assurance (QA) and Ethics Committee (EC).

Finally, the principles aim to implement the public impact levels presented by the International Association for Public Participation (IAP2) that structures suggest from informing to empowering as presented in Figure 1. Alongside the actions aforementioned, the project's aim is to empower and work side-by-side with the sectors' community to produce a product that is truthfully of use.

Figure 1. Levels of Public Engagement as per the International Association for Public Participation (IAP2)¹

3. Community Engagement

The engagement process will combine several complementary methods. Stakeholder identification will rely on partner networks, regional associations, and targeted outreach to ensure coverage of all relevant actors. The questionnaire (the questions can be found in Annex A) will be designed to capture both factual data and perceptions, allowing for nuanced analysis. Workshops will use participatory methods, including facilitated discussions and

¹ <https://www.iap2.org/page/SpectrumEvolution>

collaborative exercises, to encourage active contributions from all participants. In-person facilitation in Kenya will ensure local relevance and accessibility, while virtual participation in cross-regional sessions will connect diverse perspectives.

To strengthen the community engagement, pre-engagement interviews will be planned by December 2025. The latter can help identify baseline knowledge about the project among interested and affected parties, preferences for engagement, community groups that might otherwise be missed, and other potential issues and opportunities for the engagement process.

Follow-up communication will be a key part of the approach, with participants receiving concise reports on how their input has been used. This will help maintain trust and encourage continued engagement in later stages of the project.

All online communication initially in English will provide a sentence in Italian, French, Greek, German, and Spanish that explains how they can translate the communication presented (i.e. e-mail, newsletter, questionnaire, or other) using their digital devices.

3.1 Community and Interested Parties (*the stakeholders*)

The community refers to any individual, group of individuals, organizations directly involved in the studied sectors: members involved in the supply chain (ie. farmers, workers, providers).

The list includes:

- Operators in the sectors
- Farmers
- Miners
- Producers (ie. cooperatives)
- Equipment Suppliers
- Experts (ie. Industry Research and Development Offices)

Similarly, **interested or affected parties** are any person(s), group of individuals, or organization interested in or affected by the sectors or also researchers/experts studying the

sectors. These lateral parties who operate around or within the sectors of interest, but are not involved in the supply chain (ie. academics, consultants, experts). The list includes:

- University researchers (from diverse disciplines)
- Experts (external to the industries involved)
- NGOs involved in the sector for the informal actors (ie. waste pickers)
- Local authorities and policy-makers

This section includes stakeholders involved in sister projects who work with the parties involved in the sectors. It also includes people with an interest in the data used to shape the study.

The stakeholders are defined from WP1 and WP2, reviewing relevant literature presented in DL1.1 and DL1.2, and collected in a shared Excel sheet on the project's SharePoint. Since the SEP is made available to the public, the Excel is not linked here for privacy reasons (ie. e-mails).

3.3 Community Questionnaire

The community questionnaire will be developed where diverse interested and affected parties can offer their insight as part of the data collection effort as a preliminary pilot to test the field of the selected community and interested stakeholders.

A copy of the questionnaire can be found in Annex A and will be shared online with the possibility to use the browser to translate. Since the stakeholders are contacted via cold calls, they are free to request to not be contacted anymore.

The community questionnaire represents the first active stage of direct engagement with stakeholders in WP1 and WP3.

It is designed to gather structured information from a diverse range of interested and affected parties, providing a preliminary pilot to test the field and to validate the relevance of the themes identified through hotspot analysis.

The questionnaire will focus on two main areas: first, the digital requirements of stakeholders for the BioFairNet platform, and second, the barriers and drivers they face in advancing bio- and circular economy practices in their respective sectors.

By combining closed and open-ended questions, it will capture both quantitative data and qualitative insights, ensuring that responses are both comparable and contextually rich.

The tool will be deployed between mid-September and mid-November 2025 distributed through partner networks and platforms and sectoral associations.

Responses will be systematically analysed to inform the design of the sector-specific workshops scheduled for month fourteen and will provide the baseline evidence feeding into the co-creation model. In this way, the questionnaire functions not only as a data collection instrument but also as an early opportunity for stakeholders to engage with the project and to see their perspectives reflected in its subsequent activities.

The results collected up to M11 will feed into the DL for WP3.

3.4 Sector-Specific Workshops | Inclusion and Motivation

The workshops represent a cornerstone of the stakeholder engagement process, offering a platform for deeper dialogue that goes beyond the insights collected through the questionnaire and aims to be a constructive space for exchange. While the questionnaire provides a broad and structured overview of stakeholder needs, the workshops are designed to capture nuances, lived experiences, and collaborative ideas that can only emerge through direct interaction. They are also essential for validating preliminary findings, ensuring that the interpretation of questionnaire results aligns with the perspectives of the communities and organisations involved.

The workshops will be sector-specific, focusing separately on agricultural and mining value chains. This distinction is crucial, as the challenges, drivers, and opportunities for the bio-circular transition differ significantly across sectors. Agriculture stakeholders in regions such as the Po Valley and Andalucía face issues related to resource efficiency, monoculture dependence, and climate adaptation. Mining stakeholders in the Iberian Pyrite Belt and the

Rhenish Lignite District, on the other hand, contend with land degradation, legacy pollution, and energy transition challenges. By separating the workshops by sector and language, the engagement process ensures that discussions remain relevant, accessible, and tailored to the specific contexts of participants. Additionally, countries such as Kenya and Canada again operate on separate challenges and needs (ie. digital divide for Kenya).

Inclusion is a guiding principle of the workshops. Efforts will be made to ensure that stakeholders represent the full spectrum of each value chain, including producers, workers, cooperatives, companies, local governments, civil society organisations, and research institutions. Special attention will be given to involving voices that are often marginalised or underrepresented, such as smallholder farmers, community-based organisations, and groups representing vulnerable populations affected by mining or agricultural activities.

To support inclusivity, the workshops will be conducted in local languages (Italian, Spanish, and German) during M14, with interpretation and facilitation ensuring that all participants can engage meaningfully. In M17, two English-language workshops will provide a transnational platform for exchange, bringing together stakeholders from multiple regions.

Motivation is another critical element. For stakeholders to participate meaningfully, they must see value in their engagement. The workshops will therefore be framed not simply as data collection exercises but as opportunities for co-learning and networking. Participants will be given the chance to share their experiences, identify synergies with others facing similar challenges, and explore innovative practices that could be transferred across regions. Furthermore, each workshop will provide a feedback mechanism, where stakeholders are informed about how their contributions feed into the co-creation model and subsequent project outputs. This transparent loop of communication is intended to build trust and encourage continued collaboration. **This particular step aims to encourage their participation and help to guarantee that there is value returned to their time.**

The in-person workshop planned in Kenya is especially significant for fostering local ownership and motivation. It will provide an accessible space for stakeholders who may face barriers to online participation, ensuring that their perspectives are captured on equal footing with those of participants from Europe and Canada. In this way, the workshops

contribute not only to the collection of knowledge but also to the creation of a community of practice around bio-circular economy transitions, rooted in inclusivity, equity, and mutual learning.

3.5 Monitor and Evaluation

Objective(s)	Monitor	Evaluation
Ensure comprehensive and diverse stakeholder participation across all targeted regions and sectors	Track number and type of stakeholders included in the contact database (sector, region, organisation type, role).	Assess representativeness of stakeholders against project targets (e.g., balance between agri/mining, inclusion of SMEs, NGOs, local authorities, vulnerable groups). Personal information about the person contacted such as gender is not requested for privacy reasons and to avoid congruences in Europe with GDPR.
Collect meaningful insights through the questionnaire on digital needs and circular/bioeconomy challenges	Monitor response rates by region, sector, and stakeholder category; track completeness and quality of responses. This includes the preliminary questionnaire.	Evaluate whether the data collected adequately addresses the objectives and provides actionable inputs for workshop design
Facilitate inclusive and participatory workshops that reflect local languages and contexts	Track attendance, diversity of participants, and level of engagement during workshops (e.g., number of active interventions, feedback received)	Evaluate quality of discussions, stakeholder satisfaction (short poll at the end of each workshop) and extent to which workshops validate or enrich questionnaire findings
Build stakeholder trust and maintain motivation for continued participation	Monitor communication flow (timeliness of invitations, delivery of feedback summaries, language accessibility). This task decided with	Evaluate stakeholder feedback on clarity, transparency, and usefulness of communications; assess willingness of participants to remain engaged in future

	Ecoimagination can work to decide specific communications.	BioFairNet activities
Generate actionable outputs that can feed into the co-creation model (Task 1.5)	Monitor documentation and synthesis of questionnaire and workshop results by partners.	Evaluate whether outputs are integrated into the co-creation model, as confirmed in D.1.2 deliverable reviews and consortium feedback
External Feedback	Monitor feedback of the SEP, Questionnaire and Workshop Framework by the QAC and EC	Evaluate whether the FAIR principles and theoretical aims of the project are kept and adequately shared and implemented.

4. Strategies

4.1 Key Deadlines at a glance

- **10 - 11 September, 2025:** meetings with the Quality Assurance Committee and the Ethics Committee to review the SEP and the Questionnaire.
- **20 September - 20 November, 2025:** sharing the Questionnaire translated in Italian, Spanish, and German for the identified stakeholders to provide a preliminary collection of data.
 - **December, 2025:** Stakeholders contacted will receive a direct feedback and thank you message for filling out the survey will provide:
 - 1) possibility to join the BioFairNet Community Online;
 - 2) contact other stakeholders to network
- **1 December, 2025 - 20 January, 2026:** Identification of workshop requirements and construction
- **15 October, 2025 - 1 February, 2026:** Invitation of stakeholders to attend their related workshop based on 1) sector and 2) language

- **(M14) 10 - 15 February, 2026 (TBD):** Organisation of the following online workshops:
 - 2 Spanish-based workshops for the agri and mining sectors;
 - 1 Italian-based workshop for the agri sector;
 - 1 German-based workshop for the mining sector.
- **10 - 15 February, 2026 (TBD):** Organisation of the workshop in-person for Kenya (CUK)
- **March, 2026:** Presentation of the workshop results to the consortium and the QAC and EC.
- **March, 2026:** Stakeholders contacted will receive direct feedback and thank you message for attending the workshops and can 1) join the BioFairNet Community Online; 2) contact other stakeholders who were also contacted and/or attended the workshop(s).
- **(M17) May, 2026 (TBD):** Organisation of 2 workshops in English for the agri and mining sector. This workshop might include some improvements (if any) from the feedback from the other workshops from M14.
- **(M18) June, 2026:** Completion of the co-creation model with workshop results for the D.1.2.

Find a Gantt chart on the next page.

Gantt Chart

Months/Tasks	September - December, 2025					January - July, 2026						
Meeting with QAC and EC	█											
Sharing the Questionnaire	█	█	█									
Stakeholders Contacted				█								
Post-Questionnaire				█	█							
Preparation Workshop(s)				█	█							
Stakeholder Invitations for attending Workshop(s)			█	█	█							
Workshop(s) in Spanish, Italian, and German and in Kenya (in-person by						█						

CUK)											
Preparation Workshop in English with feedback from Stakeholders from previous workshop(s)											
Workshop(s) in English (x2)											
Completion D1.2 with results from workshops and questionnaire with the co-creation model											

4.2 Partners Involved and Task Responsibilities

Objective(s)	Partner Responsible	Deadline
Meeting with the QAC and EC	UNIFE and UNINA	September, 2025
Collecting contact information of Stakeholders of Interest	All partners	September, 2025 - January, 2026
Sharing the Questionnaire	Ecoimagination and all partners	September - November, 2025
Sharing the Invitation to the Workshops	Ecoimagination and all partners	November, 2025 - February, 2026
Sharing the Invitation to the Workshops based on single languages	<p>Ecoimagination and:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Italian (UNINA, UNITRENTO, UNIFE) 2. Spanish (SATEC) 3. German (Cologne and BIO2REG) 4. English (all partners) <p><i>The partners involved in the pilots can freely share this with the stakeholders involved in their regions.</i></p> <p><i>The in-person workshop in Kenya will be under CUK's responsibility.</i></p>	November, 2025 - February, 2026
Meeting with the QAC and EC (M15)	UNIFE and UNINA	March 2026
Sharing the Invitation to the Workshop in English (M17)	Ecoimagination and all partners	January, 2026 - May, 2026
Completion of the co-creation model (M18) for D.1.2	UNIFE, UNINA, UNITRENTO <i>This task is open for the non-EU partners to review.</i>	June, 2026

4.3 Technical Implementation

Objective(s)	Method	Partner Responsible	Deadline
Meeting with the QAC and EC	Online meeting on September 10 and 11, collecting recorded feedback	UNIFE and UNINA	September, 2025
Collecting contact information of Stakeholders of Interest	Shared Excel sheet online until September 12, 2025, to compile (and ongoing)	All partners	September, 2025 - January, 2026
Sharing the Questionnaire	[Online TBD with Ecoimagination]	Ecoimagination and all partners	September - November, 2025
Sharing the Invitation to the Workshops	[Online TBD with Ecoimagination] Draft invitations and save-the-date notices; circulate through the stakeholder database; use multiple communication channels (email, newsletters, local associations); ensure early distribution for planning. For Kenya (CUK), particular instructions will be agreed and designed for the in-person workshop and invites.	Ecoimagination and all partners	November, 2025 - February, 2026
Sharing the Invitation to the	[Online TBD with	Ecoimagination and:	November,

Workshops based on single languages	Ecoimagination] Draft invitations and save-the-date notices; circulate through the stakeholder database; use multiple communication channels (email, newsletters, local associations); ensure early distribution for planning	<p>5. Italian (UNINA, UNITRENTO, UNIFE)</p> <p>6. Spanish (SATEC)</p> <p>7. German (Cologne and BIO2REG)</p> <p>8. English (all partners)</p> <p><i>The partners involved in the pilots can freely share this with the stakeholders involved in their regions.</i></p> <p><i>The in-person workshop in Kenya will be under CUK's responsibility.</i></p>	2025 - February, 2026
Meeting with the QAC and EC (M15)	Online meeting on M15 collecting recorded feedback	UNIFE and UNINA	March 2026
Sharing the Invitation to the Workshop in English (M17)	[Online TBD with Ecoimagination] Draft invitations and save-the-date notices; circulate through the stakeholder database; use multiple communication channels (email, newsletters, local associations); ensure early distribution for	Ecoimagination and all partners	January, 2026 - May, 2026

	planning		
Completion of the co-creation model (M18) for D.1.2	Online	UNIFE, UNINA, UNITRENTO <i>This task is open for the non-EU partners to review.</i>	June, 2026

5. Appendix A | Questionnaire Questions

This form is open to stakeholders identified in the SEP that will be shared directly with the contacts collected, via project platforms, and potentially external mailing lists (where adequate). It will provide a short introduction to the project and this questionnaire. To enhance participation, the attendees will be given the chance to 1) network with other participants; 2) be the first to try the product once ready with a first version during the validation period (involving the partners from WP3 and WP6 that are involved in managing the digital backbone of the BioFairNet product and validating its use).

START SURVEY

The anonymous form can be translated using your browser and it will take at most 10 minutes.

The aim is to collect your perception on the challenges to implement environmental sustainability in the agricultural or mining sector. To identify environmental sustainability the narrows downs to circular and bio economy.

When referring to environmental sustainability, we intend the circular and bio economy as defined below:

- **Environmental Sustainability:** Sustainable development means meeting the needs of the present whilst ensuring future generations can meet their own needs ([Source EU](#)) that includes supporting the environment and reducing greenhouse gases (GHG) and other impactful activities for the Planet.
- **Circular Economy:** a system which maintains the value of products, materials and resources in the economy for as long as possible and minimizes the generation of waste. This means a system where products are reused, repaired, remanufactured or recycled ([Source EU](#)).
- **Bio Economy:** bioeconomy means using renewable biological resources from land and sea, like crops, forests, fish, animals and micro-organisms to produce food, materials, and energy ([Source EU](#)).

The data collected in this form is anonymous and stored in the project's drive. It is collected in compliance with GDPR, stored securely, and used only in aggregated and anonymised form for research and reporting purposes within the BioFairNet.

For any question regarding privacy and data sharing, email: biofairnet@unina.it

Part 1: Background information

1. Type:

- Individual (A)
- Firm or organisation (B)

2. Sector of interest (select one)

- Agricultural
- Mining

3. What role does environmental sustainability play for you and/or your organization? [Likert Scale 1-5]

- Very Important
- Important
- Moderately Important
- Slightly Important
- Not Important

4. Briefly describe your professional role

5. Describe your experience in the field of the agricultural or mining sector

6. Years of experience [defined by ranges of years]

- 0-3
- 3-5
- 5-10
- >10

Part 2: Drivers and Barriers to Environmental Sustainability Questions

for (A)

Section (a) Environmental Sustainability

- Type of organisation you represent (select one):
 - Private firm
 - Cooperative
 - Research Institute
 - University
 - Other: specify which
- Which of the following environmental (circular and bio economy) strategies do you observe being implemented the most? [Select multiple]
 - Increase the use of renewable energy sources
 - Reduce water use

- Reduce energy use
- Reduce waste generation
- Sustainable sourcing of raw materials
- Change in product design to improve recyclability
- Develop or sell products made from recovered or recycled materials
- Waste management services to transform waste into new products
- Repair, reuse, or refurbishment of products for extended life cycles
- Sharing or collaborative use of tools, equipment, or facilities
- Use of biomaterials or biobased processes in production
- Resource efficiency
- Energy efficiency
- Increased logistics efficiency
- Other (please specify)
- None of the above
- Which of the following **barriers** do you observe in the implementation of environmental (circular and bio economy) strategies? [Select multiple]
 - Poor managerial skills or lack of management commitment
 - Shortage of skilled employees
 - Lack of formalised planning processes
 - Difficulties in attracting qualified personnel
 - Difficulties developing new ideas or innovative solutions
 - Difficulties in finding collaboration partners
 - Insufficient customer demand for sustainable products/services
 - Unsupportive senior leadership
 - Insufficient participation by members/workers
 - Resistance to change among employees or members
 - Lack of short-term liquidity or financial resources
 - High fixed costs for technological investments
 - Bureaucratic impediments (internal or external)
 - Long development times for new products or services
 - Difficulties bringing new ideas to market.
 - Difficulty accessing venture capital or bank investments
 - Concerns over financial viability or profitability
 - Difficulties in updating technological knowledge
 - Other (please specify)
- Which of the following **drivers** do you observe in the implementation of environmental (circular and bio economy) strategies? [Select multiple]
 - Need to optimise operations and increase efficiency
 - Desire to improve economic results and profitability
 - Gain a competitive advantage over competitors
 - Retain customers and attract new ones
 - Respond to new standards or regulations
 - Reduce product or service costs
 - Improve sustainability and environmental performance

- Strengthen cooperative identity and member relations
- Develop new products or services for existing customers
- Develop new products or services for new customers
- Collaboration opportunities with other enterprises or institutions
- Access to external funding or investment
- Market demand for environmentally friendly goods/services
- Community or social responsibility commitments
- Other (please specify)

Leave any other comments.

Questions for (B)

Section (a) Environmental Sustainability

- Size (# employees)
- Please provide the organisation's headquarters [country]
- Please provide the country where the organisation operates (if different from headquarters) [countr(ies)]
- Describe your organisation and your role [short answer]
- Select your organisation type:
 - Cooperative
 - Part of the consortium
 - Private
 - Nonprofit
 - Public
- Which of the following best describes your organization? [Select one]
 - Produces goods
 - Provides services
 - Both (produce goods and provide services)
- Do you export (expressed as outside national boundaries)? [Y/N]
- How far does your supply and/or distribution chain extend?
 - Local
 - Regional
 - National
 - Multinational
 - Global
- Since 2021, have you invested in research and development in general? [Y/N]
- Since 2021, have you invested in research and development to implement environmental sustainability? [Y/N]
- Which of the following environmental (circular and bio economy) strategies do you implement? [Select multiple]
 - Increase the use of renewable energy sources
 - Reduce water use
 - Reduce energy use
 - Reduce waste generation
 - Sustainable sourcing of raw materials

- Change in product design to improve recyclability
- Develop or sell products made from recovered or recycled materials
- Waste management services to transform waste into new products
- Repair, reuse, or refurbishment of products for extended life cycles
- Sharing or collaborative use of tools, equipment, or facilities
- Use of biomaterials or biobased processes in production
- Other (please specify)
- None of the above
- Which of the following **barriers** do you find in the implementation of environmental (circular and bio economy) strategies? [Select multiple]
 - Poor managerial skills or lack of management commitment
 - Shortage of skilled employees
 - Lack of formalised planning processes
 - Difficulties in attracting qualified personnel
 - Difficulties developing new ideas or innovative solutions
 - Difficulties in finding collaboration partners
 - Insufficient customer demand for sustainable products/services
 - Unsupportive senior leadership
 - Insufficient participation by members/workers
 - Resistance to change among employees or members
 - Lack of short-term liquidity or financial resources
 - High fixed costs for technological investments
 - Bureaucratic impediments (internal or external)
 - Long development times for new products or services
 - Challenges in commercialising new ideas
 - Difficulty accessing venture capital or bank investments
 - Concerns over financial viability or profitability
 - Difficulties in updating technological knowledge
 - Other (please specify)
- Which of the following **drivers** do you find in the implementation of environmental (circular and bio economy) strategies? [Select multiple]
 - Need to optimise operations and increase efficiency
 - Desire to improve economic results and profitability
 - Gain a competitive advantage over competitors
 - Retain customers and attract new ones
 - Respond to new standards or regulations
 - Reduce product or service costs
 - Improve sustainability and environmental performance
 - Strengthen cooperative identity and member relations
 - Develop new products or services for existing customers
 - Develop new products or services for new customers
 - Collaboration opportunities with other enterprises or institutions
 - Access to external funding or investment

- Market demand for environmentally friendly goods/services
- Community or social responsibility commitments
- Other (please specify)

Leave any other comments.

Part 3: Digitalisation Challenges and Needs

Section (b) Digitalisation for both Type A and B Respondents

- Are you or your firm experienced in working with data platforms² ?
 - Yes
 - No

- How would you assess the need in this sector for an integrated sustainability data platform in your organization (or those within the sector)? [Likert Scale 1-5]
 - Not at all
 - A little
 - Somewhat / Maybe
 - Quite a lot
 - Very much / Absolutely yes

- If any, which digital tools does your organisation or organisations you know in the sector currently use? [Short Answer]

- If any, which challenges do you currently see in dealing with sustainability data? [Short Answer]

BioFairNet’s aim is to build a digital platform that would support stakeholders in the agricultural and mining sectors. These questions relate to your opinion and experience on the value that BioFairNet can bring.

- Which functions would be most important to you on the BioFairNet platform? [Select multiple]
 - Real-time data visualization
 - Data integration from different sources
 - Reporting on SDG targets
 - AI-supported analyses and forecasts
 - Data export / API interfaces³
 - User-friendly dashboard

² A data platform is a technology solution that enables the collection, storage, cleaning, transformation, analysis and governance of data. Data platforms can include both hardware and software components. They make it easier for organizations to use their data to improve decision making and operations. (IBM; <https://www.ibm.com/think/topics/data-platform#:~:text=A%20data%20platform%20is%20a,improve%20decision%20making%20and%20operations.>)

³ An API is an application programming interface – it is often used to exchange data and information via the internet in an automated way (machine-to-machine). Example: connecting a database (e.g., Zenodo) or a digital service (e.g., weather station) to the platform.

- Interaction with other users (data sharing, building communities, ...)
 - Collaboration tools/stakeholder integration
 - None of the following
 - Other:
- With respect to integration APIs. What external systems and tools need to be integrated with the BioFairNet platform?
 - EU and international open data repositories (Eurostat, FAOSTAT, Copernicus, EEA)
 - Research data infrastructures (Zenodo, OpenAIRE, institutional repositories)
 - Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) tools (SimaPro, OpenLCA)
 - Remote sensing and GIS platforms (Google Earth Engine, QGIS, ArcGIS)
 - Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) / supply chain management systems of partner organizations
 - Blockchain-based traceability solutions for bio/circular economy value chains
 - Decision-support and modeling tools (Input–Output tables, RAMEA/NAMEA, energy system models)
 - Collaboration and communication platforms (Teams, Slack, Nextcloud)
 - Certification and standards databases (ISO 14001, EMAS, eco-label registries)
 - National statistical offices and environmental inventories (ISPRA, INEMAR, OECD databases)
 - None of the above
 - I don't know
 - Which collaboration and co-creation functionalities are needed?
 - Shared workspaces for joint document editing and data analysis
 - Version control and change tracking for datasets, reports, and models
 - Discussion forums and thematic channels for community exchange
 - Virtual meeting rooms / video-conferencing integration
 - Interactive dashboards where stakeholders can comment or suggest changes
 - Survey and polling tools for stakeholder input and feedback
 - Co-creation boards/whiteboards (e.g. idea mapping, design thinking tools)
 - Task and project management features (assignments, deadlines, progress tracking)
 - Stakeholder mapping and engagement logs
 - Multi-language support and translation tools for inclusive participation
 - Annotation and commenting tools directly on datasets, maps, or documents
 - Secure data-sharing and access control for sensitive project information

- Knowledge repositories and best-practice libraries curated by the community
- Other:
- How often would you expect it to be necessary to use the BioFairNet platform?
 - Daily
 - Weekly
 - Monthly
 - As required
 - I think that a digital tool may NOT support the stakeholders involved in the sectors to implement the circular and bioeconomy strategies.
- Which digital features would be a game-changer for you?
 - Educational purposes
 - Connection purposes (networking)
 - Funding searches
 - Other:
- Could you describe any specific features that you expect from the BioFairNet platform or that you consider essential and that have not been mentioned in this Survey? [Short Answer]

Leave any other comment

Final Questions

- How would you like to be involved in the further development of the BioFairNet platform? (multiple answers possible)
 - Regular workshops
 - Participation in test phases
 - Provision of feedback through short surveys and/or interviews
 - No direct participation desired
- If you wish to remain in contact leave your name and e-mail:
 - Name
 - Email
- If you wish to share a contact of someone else who might be interested leave their name, e-mail, and organisation:
 - Name
 - Email
 - Organisation

For direct engagement to the workshops, we wish to inform you about specific workshops:

In February 2026, BioFairNet is organising a workshop on this topic in English, Spanish, German, and Italian. If you are interested in attending, please leave your email and organisation name. You can also select which language you would prefer. While the

workshops may focus on a specific sector and language, feel free to select all those might interest you:

- Name:
- Email:
- Language and workshop of preference: [Select Multiple]
 - English (for the agricultural and mining sector)
 - Italian (only for the agricultural sector)
 - German (only for the mining sector)

Spanish (for the agricultural and mining sector)